

Low-Complexity Resource Allocation for Task Offloading in Hierarchical Non-Terrestrial Networks

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Abstract—In this paper, we address the resource allocation problem for task offloading from Internet of Things (IoT) devices to a non-terrestrial network. The proposed architecture contains clusters of IoT devices that can either execute their computing tasks locally or offload them to a dedicated unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) functioning as a multi-access edge computing (MEC) server. The UAV can process the tasks itself or further offload them to an available high-altitude platform station (HAPS) or to a low-earth orbit (LEO) satellite within line-of-sight for remote computing. We formulate an optimization problem that aims to minimize the weighted sum of the total task-execution delay and the energy consumption of the IoT devices. Due to non-convexity of the problem and the inherent complexity-performance trade-off in optimization algorithms, we propose a set of low-complexity solutions. These include optimal methods based on convex subproblem decomposition and a greedy heuristic guided by convex optimization criteria. The framework jointly optimizes the computing resources and transmission power of IoT devices, the digital precoders and combiners at the UAV, the computing resources at the remote nodes (UAV, HAPS, and LEO), as well as task offloading decisions and subchannel allocation through a one-shot block coordinate descent approach. Simulation results highlight the performance gains of the proposed methods, demonstrating the impact of algorithmic complexity on key system metrics and the benefits of incorporating multiple non-terrestrial nodes compared to architectures lacking such capabilities.

Index Terms—multi-access edge computing (MEC), non-terrestrial networks, resource allocation, task offloading.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE Internet of things (IoT) is a paradigm characterized by a vast number of small, interconnected devices communicating via the Internet or other networks. These devices typically function as sensors, actuators, or coordinators and are widely used in monitoring and automation applications. As IoT devices are often powered by batteries, energy efficiency is a critical concern, with the goal of maximizing their operational autonomy and minimizing the frequency of recharging. Given the significant energy cost associated with local task execution, offloading computing tasks to remote servers via cellular networks offers an effective strategy for optimizing resource utilization and prolonging device lifespan [2].

This project was funded by the European Union (HORIZON-MSCA-2022-DN-01 ELIXIRION project, GA 101120135).

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An earlier version of this manuscript is to be presented at IEEE WCNC 2026 [1].

Nevertheless, terrestrial cellular coverage is not universally available. While approximately 95% of the global population is covered by cellular networks, this coverage extends to less than 45% of the Earth’s landmass [3] and only 15% of its surface area [4]. Thus, there is a lack of terrestrial infrastructure in remote or rural areas, and furthermore, existing terrestrial infrastructure may become unavailable due to traffic surges or natural disasters, and it can incur high end-to-end latency over long distances. To ensure global coverage, non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) are envisioned to provide complementary remote computing and routing services alongside terrestrial networks (TNs). NTN encompasses aerial nodes such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and high altitude platform stations (HAPS), as well as space nodes such as geostationary-orbit (GEO), medium earth-orbit (MEO) and low earth-orbit (LEO) satellites. Recognized in 3GPP Release 17 [5], NTN are envisioned to complement the terrestrial infrastructure to provide global coverage. In view of this, NTN nodes can function as multi-access edge computing (MEC) servers, offloading computing tasks from terrestrial nodes, thereby reducing the latency across wide geographic area [6]. Furthermore, NTN-based MEC service can be provided in regions where terrestrial infrastructure is either absent or temporarily unavailable. In this context, there has been increasing research interest in the integration of TNs, NTN, and MEC, particularly over the past few years [7].

Interest in using NTN for computing has grown, exemplified by the recently deployed satellite constellation by ADA Space, which aims to function as a space computing platform [8]. In particular, NTN are useful within current and future IoT contexts in remote or rural areas, such as precision agriculture, network resilience during disasters, remote monitoring or two-way messaging [7]. Their use can also be extended for ultracritical communications, such as in healthcare-related applications in remote areas [7]. In the context of healthcare, the use of NTN infrastructure can be leveraged to interconnect Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) devices, which are outside terrestrial coverage, to remote healthcare providers. Thus, the use of NTN for IoMT access becomes an enabler for Healthcare 4.0 [9].

Consequently, in recent years, there has been a growing body of literature on the use of the NTN infrastructure for task offloading. Higher-altitude satellites induce significant propagation delay, which can raise problems in the coordination of resources across the network for task offloading purposes. Thus, LEO satellites are usually considered for direct access to ground and aerial nodes, although their resources are limited. Moreover, offloading tasks directly from lightweight single-

antenna IoT devices to LEO satellites may be prohibitive in terms of the transmit power needed for reliable reception. In this context, UAVs can be helpful in gathering local IoT-generated data and computing the associated tasks, or to further offload them to a LEO satellite. Contrasting their ad-hoc deployment, advantageous line-of-sight (LoS) component, and maneuverability, their main drawbacks are their limited coverage, limited resources and short flight times. To alleviate this, HAPSs, which are located at an altitude range of 20 to 50 km, and fixed with respect to the surface of Earth [10] can have large payloads, longer flight times, and higher computing capacity to help in task offloading scenarios, although with coverage areas lower than those of LEO satellites. Given that LEO satellites, HAPS, and UAVs each present distinct advantages and limitations, it is sensible to consider a multi-layer MEC architecture that integrates all these platforms.

Optimizing the resources of such a heterogeneous network for task offloading **entails** high complexity and coordination delay when considering centralized approaches. Hence, sub-optimal distributed approaches are needed to ensure scalability. To this end, this work considers a multi-layered network for task offloading of tasks generated by ground IoT nodes, in which the resources of the network, such as subchannel allocation, precoder and combiner design, power allocation, computing resources and offloading decision, are optimized to minimize the total delay of the tasks, as well as the energy consumption of the IoT devices. Low-complexity algorithms are designed within a distributed scheme, considering the delays due to the levels of distribution of the resource allocation algorithm.

A. Related Work

There is extensive literature on the allocation of MEC resources, such as segment selection and caché [?] service placement [?] and demand-aware caching [?]. Particularly, the resource allocation in NTN for task offloading is a research area that has raised interest in the last years. Considering single-layer solutions, [11] jointly optimizes the deployment and task offloading for MEC-enabled LAPs, [12] optimizes LAP deployment, IoT device association, task offloading and resource allocation in an industrial IoT setting, whereas in [13] the optimization of task offloading, computing resources, caching decisions and bandwidth in a HAPS-assisted and MEC-enabled intelligent transportation system, is considered. For LEO-enabled task offloading, while [14] considers the joint optimization of bandwidth and transmit power for LEO-assisted task offloading of data generated by IoT devices, [15] performs the joint optimization of association, transmit power, task scheduling and bandwidth in a three-tier satellite MEC, ground cloud infrastructure. Moreover, multi-layered NTNs have also been studied, such as in [16] where the computation offloading and resource allocation are jointly optimized in a multi-layer NTN with MEC-enabled HAPS connected through a LEO-enabled backhaul, and [17], which considers the joint optimization of access strategy, transmit power, computing resources and offloading in a space-air-ground integrated network.

B. Motivation and Contributions

Existing literature on NTN integration considers iterative centralized coordination [18], [19], [20], or iterative distributed solutions which need global convergence [21], [16], [17]. In the presence of satellites, which are located at very high altitudes, the delay induced by the signaling and resource allocation algorithm runtime becomes relevant. However, the existing works do not consider this delay into the optimization problem, which can lead to issues in delay-sensitive tasks.

Furthermore, when considering several types of NTN nodes, their differing characteristics need to be specified. In terms of computing capabilities, HAPS may have large computing resources available, while the most realistic scenario for LEO satellites is to have limited computing resources due to their relatively smaller sizes and radiation-tolerant electrical components. On the other hand, with the exception of works such as [20] and [22], smooth antenna radiation patterns, which characterize coverage areas, are usually not considered in NTN nodes. Even the mentioned works do not account for antenna radiation patterns in HAPSs. A consideration of these characteristics may yield more insightful results in the task offloading under such heterogeneous networks.

The main focus of our work is to deal with the difficulty of coordinating resources across an NTN which is a wide-spanning resource-constrained network by proposing a simplified network architecture as well as low-complexity algorithms and frameworks that allow for a more efficient resource allocation procedure, and resource utilization. We aim to simplify the coordination in the proposed network while tackling challenges regarding low computing resources, heterogeneous coverage, algorithmic and signaling complexity and scalability.

Thus, and expanding upon previous literature, we propose a 4-layer TN-NTN for task offloading of computing tasks generated by ground IoT nodes to UAVs serving as their first point of contact, which can compute tasks or further offload them to a computing resourceful HAPS or to a wide coverage LEO satellite, both having varying MEC capabilities. In our work, we consider smooth antenna radiation patterns for the LEO satellite as well as the HAPS to examine the offloading preference based on smooth coverage areas, as well as varying available resources. To accommodate tasks generated irregularly or sporadically, we propose the inclusion of the algorithm runtime delay into the problem formulation. In order to solve the offloading and resource allocation problem efficiently in terms of the algorithm runtime delay, we develop low-complexity algorithms based on convex optimization criteria and techniques such as the quadratic transform (QT). We include a summary in Table I, which highlights our contribution compared to the referenced state-of-the-art. We consider low complexity as heuristics with low number of iterations or (non-nested) interior point methods. We consider non-low complexity deep-learning solutions due to the long training time for a specific network architecture, and also extensive iterative algorithms such as SCA, GBD or BSUM.

The contributions of this work are summarized as:

- We propose a MEC-enabled hierarchical TN-NTN archi-

TABLE I
SUMMARY ON STATE OF THE ART.

	UAV	HAPS	LEO	Energy	Delay	Coverage	Low-complexity	Solution	Algorithm runtime delay
[11]	X				X		X	BCD with IPM	
[12]	X			X				DRL	
[23]	X			X				SCA	
[13]		X			X			MADRL	
[24]	X			X		X	X	Convex Opt. Heuristic	
[14]			X	X	X	X		MADRL	
[25]			X	X				DNN & SCA	
[22]	X		X	X		X	X	BCD Dual Method & IPM	
[15]			X	X			X	Convex Opt. & IPM	
[21]	X	X						MADRL	
[16]		X	X	X	X			DRL	
[26]	X	X		X			X	K-Means IPM	
[17]		X	X	X	X			GBD & SCA	
[18]	X		X		X			BSUM	
[19]	X		X	X	X	X		DRL	
[20]		X	X	X		X		BCD Difference of Convex	
[27]	X		X					DRL	
Our work	X	Convex Opt. Heuristic	X						

texture that accounts for smooth coverage areas of the NTN nodes. This system is composed of 4-layers, where UAVs coordinate local IoT nodes for task offloading, computing either locally, at the UAVs, at a HAPS or at a LEO satellite.

- We formulate an optimization problem, which seeks to minimize the weighted sum delay of the tasks and energy consumption of the IoT nodes in such a way that allows for a proper treatment through convex optimization-based solutions. The delays are weighted by their maximum allowed delays to ensure a level of fairness across tasks. Furthermore, the problem is constrained on the maximum delay of the tasks.
- As a solution to the problem, we design a multi-stage low-complexity algorithm for optimizing over the precoder and combiner designs, the transmit power, the subchannel allocation, the computing resources and the task offloading decision. The algorithm is based on an alternating optimization scheme, where each stage is solved by convex optimization techniques, and can be performed at different levels of distribution across the nodes in the system.
- We propose a novel convex optimization-based greedy algorithm for the joint subchannel allocation and offloading decision problem, based on the quadratic transform, which is a state-of-the art transformation for fractional programs.
- For the greedy algorithm we propose the over-advertising of resources of remote low-resources MEC-enabled nodes, in order to incentivize offloading to them.
- We propose several levels of distribution for our algorithm, which gives flexibility to its operation, accounting for the delay introduced by the signaling needed to solve the problem in a distributed manner.
- We provide simulation results that show the improvement of utilizing the 4-layer architecture compared with architectures with less nodes, with other state-of-the-art algorithms. We also show the impact of the algorithm

runtime delay on the resource allocation results, and we show the improvement of utilizing simple suboptimal algorithms under certain conditions of the system.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II introduces the system model together with the parameters of interest, while Section III presents the optimization problem to be solved. Section IV develops the alternating optimization algorithm. In Section V simulation results are presented, and finally, in Section VI conclusions are drawn.

Notation: The following notation is used throughout this manuscript: vectors are column-vectors by default and are written as bold lowercase letters (e.g. \mathbf{h}), matrices are written as bold uppercase letters (e.g. \mathbf{U}), sets are written as italic uppercase letters (e.g. \mathcal{I}), the upper script $(\cdot)^T$ denotes the transpose of the vector, \odot represents the Hadamard product of two matrices or vectors, $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm of a vector, \mathbb{R} is the set of real numbers, \mathbb{R}_+ is the set of non-negative real numbers, \mathbb{C} is the set of complex numbers, $[\cdot]$ defines a vector or matrix and $\{\cdot\}$ defines a set.

For convenience, a list of important symbols used throughout this manuscript is presented in Table II.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a set of ground IoT devices $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, I\}$ separated in geographically distant clusters. A UAV from a set of UAVs $\mathcal{U} = \{1, \dots, U\}$ is assigned to each cluster, so the set of devices associated with the UAV u is written as $\mathcal{I}_u \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ with $|\mathcal{I}_u| = I_u$ and $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} I_u = I$. To complement the computing capabilities of the IoT devices, there is a HAPS h and a LEO satellite s that can act as MEC servers, while the HAPS can also serve as a coordinator across UAVs. The antenna elements in the antenna arrays at the HAPS and LEO satellite exhibit a smooth radiation pattern, such as in [20], which affects the range of the scanning beams of the arrays, determining their coverage areas. The UAVs are assumed to receive a minimum level of service, which allows them to exchange signaling information with both the HAPS and LEO satellite through channels in the same band. Each node is located in Cartesian

TABLE II
NOMENCLATURE

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{I}	Set of all IoT nodes in the system
\mathcal{I}_u	Set of IoT nodes (tasks) associated to UAV u
\mathcal{I}^k	Set of tasks computed at remote node $k \in \{h, s\}$
\mathcal{I}_u^k	Set of tasks offloaded from UAV u to remote node $k \in \{h, s\}$
\mathcal{U}	Set of UAVs in the system
\mathcal{R}	Set of remote computing nodes in the system
ψ_i	Task generated by IoT node i
d_i	Size of task ψ_i in bits
c_i	computing density of task ψ_i in cycles per bit
τ_i^{\max}	Maximum delay of task ψ_i in seconds
\mathcal{B}	Set of subchannels available between IoT nodes and UAVs
B_u	Bandwidth of IoT-UAV subchannels
B_h	Bandwidth of UAV-HAPS channels
B_s	Bandwidth of UAV-LEO channels
$\rho_{i,u}^b$	Indicator variable of offloading from IoT device i to UAV u through subchannel b
$\beta_{u,k}^i$	Indicator variable of offloading task ψ_i from UAV u to node $k \in \{h, s\}$
$\tau_{j,k}$	Delay due to transmission between node $j \in \mathcal{I} \cup \mathcal{U}$ and $k \in \mathcal{R}$
τ_i^k	Delay due to computing task ψ_i at node $k \in \mathcal{I} \cup \mathcal{R}$
$\tau_{i \rightarrow j}$	Delay due to offloading task ψ_i from i to node $k \in \mathcal{R}$
τ_{op}	Algorithm runtime delay
E_i	Energy consumed by local computing of task ψ_i at node i
$E_{i,u}$	Energy consumed by transmitting task ψ_i to UAV u
$R_{i,u}^b$	Communication rate between IoT device i and UAV u through subchannel b
$R_{u,k}$	Communication rate between UAV u and node $k \in \{h, s\}$
$\varepsilon_E, \varepsilon_\tau$	Energy and delay weighting hyperparameters
P_k	Maximum transmit power of node k
σ_k	Non-zero singular value of channel between UAV and node $k \in \{h, s\}$
$p_{i,u}^b$	Transmission power of IoT device i to UAV u through subchannel b
$p_{u,k}$	Transmission power of UAV u to node $k \in \{h, s\}$
\mathbf{r}_k	Cartesian coordinates of node k
f_i^k	Computing resources allocated to task ψ_i at node k
F_k^{\max}	Total computing resources at node k
$F_{k,u}^{\max}$	Total computing resources of node k advertised to UAV u

Fig. 1. System model.

coordinates $\mathbf{r}_k = [x_k, y_k, z_k]^T$, with $k \in \mathcal{I} \cup \mathcal{U} \cup \{h, s\}$. A representation of the system can be seen in Fig. 1.

In a snapshot of the system, the IoT devices generate tasks irregularly, which need to be computed. Each task is

represented as $\psi_i = [d_i, c_i, \tau_i^{\max}]$, where d_i is the number of bits in the task, c_i is its computing density (in CPU cycles per bit), which depends on the application [28], and τ_i^{\max} is its maximum tolerable delay (in seconds). Given that a task is uniquely associated to an IoT device, the script i will be used to represent a task or its corresponding IoT device interchangeably. An IoT device computes the task locally or offloads it to their local UAV, which acts as a MEC server and local coordinator for the cluster. The UAV can either compute the task or further offload it to the HAPS or to the LEO satellite for remote computing. Thus, the set of remote computing nodes is $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{U} \cup \{h, s\}$. Task ψ_i is dependent on the data gathered and application required by the corresponding IoT device. Thus, the task could be partitionable or non-partitionable. In practice, tasks can be partitioned into a given number of sub-tasks, and each would need to be allocated to a computing node for processing individually. In that sense, we consider binary offloading, as a general scheme that may apply to both types of tasks.

Within a cluster, a UAV communicates with its associated IoT devices through orthogonal subchannels $\mathcal{B} = \{1, \dots, B\}$, each of bandwidth B_u . In remote areas the spectrum is not used extensively, for which there is no need for high frequency reuse, allowing for orthogonal access. Thus, each IoT device occupies at most one orthogonal subchannel and no inter-IoT device interference is present. Due to the geographical separation among clusters and the directivity of the antenna arrays of the NTN nodes, we assume that no interference is present between clusters. For purposes of communication and signaling, the IoT devices are single-antenna devices, while UAVs have a uniform linear arrays (ULAs) of N_u^{ULA} antenna elements. For communication between UAVs and the HAPS or LEO satellite, the UAVs have an upward-facing uniform planar array (UPA) of N_u^{UPA} antenna elements, while the HAPS and the LEO satellite have downward facing UPAs of N_h and N_s antenna elements respectively. They communicate through orthogonal subchannels, which implies no interference between the corresponding links. Within this snapshot of the system, we assume that the position and trajectory of each UAV has been previously determined to serve their assigned cluster. Moreover, we assume that the Doppler shift from the signals sent by the UAVs to the LEO satellite, due to the high velocities the latter travels at, is either compensated at the UAV or at the LEO satellite.

A. Communication Model

Let $\mathbf{v}_{u,i}^b \in \mathbb{C}^{N_u^{\text{ULA}}}$ with $\|\mathbf{v}_{u,i}^b\|_2 = 1$ be the combiner associated with UAV u and device i over subchannel b . Assuming orthogonal access, and a quasi-static channel in the S band $\mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b \in \mathbb{C}^{N_u^{\text{ULA}}}$, and transmission power $p_{i,u}^b$, the instantaneous corresponding channel capacity is given as

$$R_{i,u}^b = B_u \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|\mathbf{v}_{u,i}^{b,H} \mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b|^2 p_{i,u}^b}{\|\mathbf{v}_{u,i}^b\|_2^2 B_u N_0} \right), \quad (1)$$

where N_0 is the noise power per unit bandwidth at reception. Let $\rho_{i,u}^b$ be a binary variable indicating if subchannel b is allocated to device i by UAV u ($\rho_{i,u}^b = 1$), or not ($\rho_{i,u}^b =$

0). Then, for convenience, the instantaneous channel capacity between i and u can be written as

$$R_{i,u} = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b. \quad (2)$$

An IoT device can offload its task to its corresponding UAV through at most one subchannel. To maintain orthogonality between IoT devices, a given subchannel can be allocated to at most one IoT device. These constraints are expressed as

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (4)$$

Leveraging the more simplified coordination between the UAVs and the HAPS or LEO satellite, it is assumed that the UAVs offload tasks to these nodes through links in the Ka band, which are orthogonal of bandwidth B_h and B_s correspondingly. UAV u employs the precoder $\mathbf{w}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_u^{\text{UPA}}}$ to offload all of the intended tasks to node $k \in \{h, s\}$, and node k applies the combiner $\mathbf{v}_{k,u} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_k}$, with $\|\mathbf{v}_{k,u}\|_2 = 1$, to receive it. Let $\mathbf{H}_{u,k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_k \times N_u^{\text{UPA}}}$ be the corresponding channel matrix, then the capacity of the channel between UAV u and k is given as

$$R_{u,k} = B_k \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|\mathbf{v}_{k,u}^H \mathbf{H}_{u,k} \mathbf{w}_{u,k}|^2}{\|\mathbf{v}_{k,u}\|_2^2 B_k N_0} \right). \quad (5)$$

Let $\beta_{u,k}^i$ is a binary variable indicating if task i is offloaded from UAV u to the node k ($\beta_{u,k}^i = 1$) or not ($\beta_{u,k}^i = 0$). A task can only be offloaded to remote node k , if it has been offloaded to the corresponding UAV beforehand. Furthermore, a task can be offloaded to only one of the two remote nodes: the HAPS or to the LEO satellite. Thus, it must hold that

$$\beta_{u,s}^i + \beta_{u,h}^i \leq \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u. \quad (6)$$

B. Channel Model

The air-to-ground (A2G) channel response between an IoT device $i \in \mathcal{I}_u$ and a UAV $u \in \mathcal{U}$ through subchannel $b \in \mathcal{B}$ is given by $\mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b = \sqrt{L_{i,u}^{-1}} \bar{\mathbf{h}}_{i,u}^b$. $L_{i,u}$ is the pathloss between i and u , and the small-scale fading component $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{i,u}^b$ is modeled as Rician fading as in [29]. Furthermore, the average A2G path loss $L_{i,u}$ is given as in [30].

Given the spatial sparsity of the links between the upward facing UPAs of the flying UAVs, and the downward facing UPA of the HAPS and the LEO satellite, these channels are modeled as LoS channels which undergo free-space pathloss. Thus, the channel between UAV u and node $k \in \{h, s\}$ is given as

$$\mathbf{H}_{u,k} = \left(\frac{\lambda_k g_k(\theta_{u,k}) \sqrt{G_{u,k}}}{4\pi \|\mathbf{r}_u - \mathbf{r}_k\|} \right) \mathbf{a}_{k,u}^{\text{AoA}} (\mathbf{a}_{u,k}^{\text{AoD}})^H, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{k,u}^{\text{AoA}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_k}$ and $\mathbf{a}_{u,k}^{\text{AoD}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_u^{\text{UPA}}}$ are the beamsteering vectors for the corresponding AoA and angle of departure (AoD). $G_{u,k}$ includes the atmospheric losses caused

by weather phenomena in the troposphere, considering that the HAPS and LEO satellite are located above it. The term $g_k(\theta_{u,k})$ models the normalized radiation pattern of the receive antenna elements of node k , which is considered common to all of them, given the large distances. For the LEO antenna array, we consider horn-type antenna elements as commercially available [31]. For this type of array, we choose a Bessel-based radiation pattern given as [32], [33]

$$g_s(\theta_{u,s}) = \frac{J_1(u_{u,s})}{2u_{u,s}} + 36 \frac{J_3(u_{u,s})}{u_{u,s}^3}, \quad (8)$$

$$u_{u,s} = \frac{\pi D}{\lambda_s} \sin(\theta_{u,s}), \quad (9)$$

where D is the aperture dimension of the antenna elements and $\theta_{u,s}$ is the elevation angle between UAV u and the LEO satellite. For the HAPS, we consider a patch antenna array as considered in the literature [34] [35] and in commercial models [36]. For this type of array, we consider a cosine radiation pattern given as

$$g_h(\theta_{u,h}) = \cos(\theta_{u,h})^n, \quad (10)$$

where the exponent n controls how wide or narrow the main beam of the radiation pattern is, and $\theta_{u,h}$ is the elevation angle between UAV u and the HAPS.

To account for the high mobility of the LEO satellite, we denote the corresponding beamsteering vectors as a function of time. Thus, $\mathbf{a}_{s,u}^{\text{AoA}} = \mathbf{a}_{s,u}^{\text{AoA}}(t + \tau_{u,s}^{\text{prop}})$ and $\mathbf{a}_{u,s}^{\text{AoD}} = \mathbf{a}_{u,s}^{\text{AoD}}(t)$ denote the AoA and AoD beamsteering vectors at time t , and $t + \tau_{u,s}^{\text{prop}}$ respectively, where $\tau_{u,s}^{\text{prop}}$ is the propagation time between UAV u and the LEO satellite, which is not negligible due to the large distance between the two nodes.

C. Delay Model

The sources of delay considered when offloading and computing a task are the delay induced by the transmission of the tasks via the wireless medium, and the delay induced by the computing of the task at the corresponding computing node. Furthermore, we also consider the delay induced by the signaling and resource allocation algorithm runtime, which comes previous to the task offloading itself. The delay of the reporting of the task results is typically not considered due to their small size compared to the size of the task.

1) *Transmission Delay*: This delay is induced by the transmission of the tasks from the IoT devices to the UAVs, or from the UAVs to the HAPS or LEO satellite.

a) *IoT - UAV*: The transmission delay experienced by offloading task ψ_i from device i to UAV u is given as

$$\tau_{i,u} = \frac{d_i}{R_{i,u}} = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b}. \quad (11)$$

b) *UAV - HAPS*: The transmission delay experienced by offloading the required tasks from UAV u to the HAPS, is

$$\tau_{u,h} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,h}^i d_i}{R_{u,h}}. \quad (12)$$

c) *UAV - LEO*: For transmissions between the low-altitude UAVs and the LEO satellite, the round-trip propagation delay cannot be neglected, due to the large distances considered. It follows that the delay due to the offloading of tasks from UAV u to s is the sum of the transmission delay and the propagation delay, given as

$$\tau_{u,s} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,s}^i d_i}{R_{u,s}} + 2 \underbrace{\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{c}}_{\tau_{u,s}^{\text{prop}}}. \quad (13)$$

2) *Computing Delay*: The computing of task ψ_i can be performed locally at the corresponding IoT device $i \in \mathcal{I}$, or remotely at the UAVs $u \in \mathcal{U}$, the HAPS h or the LEO satellite s . If node $k \in \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{I}$ computes task ψ_i , the corresponding computing delay is given as

$$\tau_i^k = \frac{d_i c_i}{f_i^k}, \quad (14)$$

where f_i^k represents the resources allocated for task ψ_i by node k .

3) *Algorithm Runtime Delay*: For real-time task offloading, the runtime of the resource allocation algorithm must also be taken into account. To compute the algorithm runtime delay, we denote the number of basic operations that it performs (additions, multiplications and divisions¹) as o_{op} . Then, we determine the number of CPU cycles that are spent per operation as c_{op} , which is a parameter of the processor, and it depends on parameters such as the type of processor, number of cores and operation units [37].

a) *Centralized execution*: the algorithm runtime delay for centralized execution at node k is given as

$$\tau_{op} = \frac{o_{op} c_{op}}{F_k^{\max}} + \tau_k^{\text{RTT}}. \quad (15)$$

We consider F_k^{\max} to be the total computing capacity of node k , which runs the algorithm and τ_k^{RTT} is the maximum round trip time between ground nodes and the computing node. The transmissions times are not taken into account, since the signaling overhead is assumed to be of much lower size than the tasks.

b) *Parallel distributed execution*: assuming nodes \mathcal{K} execute the entire algorithm in parallel, the corresponding runtime delay is given as

$$\tau_{op} = \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\{ \frac{o_{op}^k c_{op}^k}{F_k^{\max}} + \tau_k^{\text{RTT}} \right\} + \tau_{k'}^{\text{RTT}}, \quad (16)$$

where τ_k^{RTT} is the round-trip delay between node k and the node in charge of distributing the computing across \mathcal{K} , and $\tau_{k'}^{\text{RTT}}$ is the round-trip delay between such an aggregator node, and the ground nodes.

¹Usually, divisions are considered with a different number of cycles, but for simplicity we will include them with the other basic operations.

c) *Sequential distributed execution*: assume the algorithm is executed in T stages, and for each stage t , a possible different set of nodes \mathcal{K}_t executes it in parallel. In such a scenario, the corresponding runtime delay is given as

$$\tau_{op} = \sum_{t=1}^T \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}_t} \left\{ \frac{o_{op,t}^k c_{op,t}^k}{F_k^{\max}} + \tau_{k,t+1}^{\text{prop}} \right\}, \quad (17)$$

in which $\tau_{k,t+1}^{\text{prop}}$ is the propagation time between node k and the following aggregator node at time $t+1$, and $\tau_{k,T+1}^{\text{prop}}$ is the propagation time to reach the ground nodes.

D. Energy Consumption Model

We focus on the energy consumption at the IoT devices, due to their reliance on batteries, in order to reduce their charging periods and extend their life-spans. In this context, there are two main sources of energy consumption: due to transmission of tasks from IoT nodes to the UAVs, and due to local computing of the tasks.

1) *Transmission Energy Consumption*: The energy consumed by the IoT device i due to the transmission of its task to its corresponding UAV is given by

$$E_{i,u} = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b p_{i,u}^b \tau_{i,u} = \left(\frac{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b p_{i,u}^b}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} \right) d_i. \quad (18)$$

2) *Computing Energy Consumption*: The energy consumed to compute task ψ_i by its corresponding IoT device is given as

$$E_i = \kappa_i d_i c_i (f_i^i)^2, \quad (19)$$

which is a widely used model for low CPU voltage devices, applicable to IoT devices where the computing power grows with the third power of the computing frequency [38]. Here, κ_i is the effective switched capacitance of the CPU.

E. Performance Metrics

We consider the IoT nodes as power-constrained devices, which benefit from the efficient use of their battery, thus, one objective is to extend their battery life. The energy consumption of all of the IoT devices, due to the offloading and computing of every task is given as

$$E = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left(\left(1 - \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \right) E_i + \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \right) E_{i,u} \right). \quad (20)$$

Although maximum latency constraints may be enforced, it is of interest to prioritize the quick completion of the tasks as much as possible, particularly when battery conditions at the devices are favorable. However, given the maximum delay constraint that may vary between tasks, optimization may prioritize tasks with longer delay constraints. To incentivize the solution of the optimization problem to provide a similar delay for every task relative to their maximum delay, a weighted sum delay of the tasks is considered as

$$\hat{\tau} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{1}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \right) \tau_{i,u} + \beta_{u,h}^i \tau_{u,h} + \beta_{u,s}^i \tau_{u,s} \right) + \left(1 - \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \right) \tau_i^i + \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b - \beta_{u,h}^i - \beta_{u,s}^i \right) \tau_i^u$$

$$+ \sum_{k \in \{h,s\}} \beta_{u,k}^i \tau_i^k + \tau_{op} \Big). \quad (21)$$

Then, the metric we select to optimize is the total weighted energy consumption and task delay, given as

$$\Phi = \varepsilon_E E + \varepsilon_\tau \hat{\tau}, \quad (22)$$

where ε_E and ε_τ are non-negative hyperparameters that can be tuned depending on the current requirements of the system, with $\varepsilon_E + \varepsilon_\tau = 1$ without loss of generality. This method of weighted addition of two different metrics for optimization is widely used for multi-objective optimization, in particular for resource allocation problems such as in [14], [16] and [39].

We decompose the objective function per task as $\Phi = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \Phi_i$, such that it takes the form of $\Phi_i = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau \tau_{op}}{\tau_i^{\max}} + \Phi_i^u + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \Phi_i^u + \beta_{u,h}^i \Phi_i^h + \beta_{u,s}^i \Phi_i^s$, where each term represents the objective function value from offloading and computing the task at a certain node. Namely, Φ_i^u represents the value of computing the task locally, and is given as

$$\Phi_i^u = \left(f_i^i\right)^2 \varepsilon_E \kappa_i d_i c_i + \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{f_i^i \tau_i^{\max}}. \quad (23)$$

Then, Φ_i^u represents the value of offloading and computing the task at the corresponding UAV, given as

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_i^u &= \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^u} - \frac{1}{f_i^i} \right) - \left(f_i^i\right)^2 \varepsilon_E \kappa_i d_i c_i \\ &+ \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_u} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} + \varepsilon_E d_i \left(\frac{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_u} \rho_{i,u}^b P_{i,u}^b}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_u} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

And, Φ_i^k , with $k \in \{h, s\}$, represents the value of further offloading and computing the task at the HAPS or LEO satellite, given as

$$\Phi_i^h = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^h} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,h}^j \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_j}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{R_{u,h}}, \quad (25)$$

$$\Phi_i^s = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^s} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,s}^j \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_j}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{R_{u,s}} + \frac{2\varepsilon_\tau \|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{\tau_i^{\max} c}. \quad (26)$$

These expressions contain negative terms, which serve to cancel the corresponding positive term from previous expressions. For example, if a task is computed at the UAV, the terms corresponding to the local IoT computing of the task need to be canceled, which is expressed as the corresponding negative terms in Φ_i^u .

Similarly, the per-task delay is expressed as $\tau_i = \tau_{op} + \tau_i^u + \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \bar{\tau}_i^u + \beta_{u,h}^i \bar{\tau}_i^h + \beta_{u,s}^i \bar{\tau}_i^s$, where each term represents the delay due to offloading and computing a task at a certain node. Here, $\bar{\tau}_i^u$ represents the delay due to offloading and computing the task at the corresponding UAV is given as

$$\bar{\tau}_i^u = d_i c_i \left(\frac{1}{f_i^u} - \frac{1}{f_i^i} \right) + d_i \frac{1}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}_u} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b}. \quad (27)$$

Moreover, the delay due to further offloading and computing the task at the HAPS or the LEO satellite are given as

$$\bar{\tau}_i^h = d_i c_i \left(\frac{1}{f_i^h} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \beta_{u,h}^j d_j \frac{1}{R_{u,h}}, \quad (28)$$

$$\bar{\tau}_i^s = d_i c_i \left(\frac{1}{f_i^s} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \beta_{u,s}^j d_j \frac{1}{R_{u,s}} + \frac{2\|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{c}. \quad (29)$$

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We aim to minimize the objective function Φ by leveraging the subchannel allocation of the UAVs, the transmit precoding and receive combining of the nodes involved in offloading transmissions, computing resources at the computing nodes and the offloading decisions for every task. Let $\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}} = [\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_I]$, with $\mathbf{p}_i = [p_{i,u}^1, \dots, p_{i,u}^B]^T$, $\mathbf{W}^{\text{UAV}} = [\mathbf{w}_{1,h}, \mathbf{w}_{1,s}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{U,h}, \mathbf{w}_{U,s}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{UAV}} = [\mathbf{v}_{u,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{u,I_u}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{HAPS}} = [\mathbf{v}_{h,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{h,U}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{LEO}} = [\mathbf{v}_{s,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{s,U}]$, $\mathbf{P}_u = [\boldsymbol{\rho}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\rho}_I]$ with $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i = [\rho_{i,u}^1, \dots, \rho_{i,u}^B]^T$. Let $\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}} = [\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_I]$, with $\mathbf{p}_i = [p_{i,u}^1, \dots, p_{i,u}^B]^T$, $\mathbf{W}^{\text{UAV}} = [\mathbf{w}_{1,h}, \mathbf{w}_{1,s}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{U,h}, \mathbf{w}_{U,s}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{UAV}} = [\mathbf{v}_{u,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{u,I_u}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{HAPS}} = [\mathbf{v}_{h,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{h,U}]$, $\mathbf{V}^{\text{LEO}} = [\mathbf{v}_{s,1}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{s,U}]$, $\Upsilon_u = [\boldsymbol{\rho}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\rho}_I]$ with $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i = [\rho_{i,u}^1, \dots, \rho_{i,u}^B]^T$. Then, let $\Xi_u = [\boldsymbol{\beta}_{u,h}, \boldsymbol{\beta}_{u,s}]$, with $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{u,k} = [\beta_{u,k}^1, \dots, \beta_{u,k}^{I_u}]^T$ for $k \in \{h, s\}$. Finally, let $\mathbf{f} = [f_1^1, \dots, f_I^I]^T$ and $\mathbf{F} = [\mathbf{f}^1, \dots, \mathbf{f}^U, \mathbf{f}^h, \mathbf{f}^s]$, with $\mathbf{f}^k = [f_1^k, \dots, f_I^k]^T$ for $k \in \{u, h, s\}$. Defining $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}}, \mathbf{W}^{\text{UAV}}, \{\mathbf{V}_u^{\text{UAV}}\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}, \mathbf{V}^{\text{HAPS}}, \mathbf{V}^{\text{LEO}}, \{\Upsilon_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}, \{\Xi_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{F}\}$, the optimization problem to be solved is formulated as follows:

$$\mathcal{P} : \min_{\mathcal{S}} \Phi \quad (30a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } C_1 : \|\mathbf{w}_{u,h}\|_2^2 + \|\mathbf{w}_{u,s}\|_2^2 \leq P_u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \quad (30b)$$

$$C_2 : \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} p_{i,u}^b \leq P_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (30c)$$

$$C_3 : 0 \leq f_i^i \leq F_i^{\max}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (30d)$$

$$C_4 : \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} f_i^k \leq F_k^{\max}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{R} \quad (30e)$$

$$C_5 : \tau_i \leq \tau_i^{\max}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (30f)$$

$$C_6 : \rho_{u,h}^i, \beta_{u,s}^i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \quad (30g)$$

$$C_7 : \rho_{i,u}^b \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u, \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (30h)$$

$$C_8 : \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (30i)$$

$$C_9 : \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (30j)$$

$$C_{10} : \beta_{u,s}^i + \beta_{u,h}^i \leq \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (30k)$$

$$C_{11} : p_{i,u}^b \geq 0, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u, \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (30l)$$

$$C_{12} : f_i^u, f_i^k \geq 0, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u, k \in \{h, s\}, \quad (30m)$$

where C_1 constrains the available transmit power at the UAV, C_2 is a constraint on the total available transmit power at the IoT devices, C_3 and C_4 constrain the maximum computing resources available locally at the IoT nodes and at the remote nodes correspondingly, C_5 constrains the maximum delay of every task, C_6 and C_7 indicate that the decision variables are binary, C_8 indicates that an IoT device accesses its local UAV through at most one subchannel, C_9 indicates that every IoT-UAV subchannel is occupied by at most one IoT device, and C_{10} indicates that offloading of a task from a UAV to the HAPS or the LEO satellite is only possible if the task has been previously offloaded to it. It is also worth noting that the maximum computing power at the nodes is implicitly constrained by their maximum computing resources constraint.

A. Reduction of Degrees of Freedom

We can simplify the problem by computing unit-power precoders (and combiners) that maximize the communication rates, while retaining the transmit powers as degrees of freedom. A subchannel is allocated utmost to one device, hence, the IoT-UAV device rate expression in (1) is maximized by a maximum ratio combiner (MRC), which is achieved by setting the combiner as $\mathbf{v}_{u,i}^b = \mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b$, obtaining

$$R_{i,u}^b = B_u \log_2 \left(1 + p_{i,u}^b \frac{\|\mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b\|^2}{B_u N_0} \right). \quad (31)$$

The LoS-MIMO channel matrices of the UAV-HAPS/LEO links are rank-deficient, having only array gain. Thus, the rates in (5) are maximized by means of singular value decomposition (SVD). Given that the matrices are rank-1, there is a single non-zero singular value, of which its singular vectors correspond to their AoA and AoD beamsteering vectors. Then, the maximum communication rates are obtained by aligning the precoders and combiners to the corresponding AoA and AoD vectors. In particular, the UAV-LEO channel $\mathbf{H}_{u,s}(t + \tau_{op})$ can be formed analytically with the corresponding vectors after algorithm runtime. The resulting rates to remote nodes $k \in \{h, s\}$ are given as

$$R_{u,k} = B_k \log_2 \left(1 + p_{u,k} \frac{\sigma_k^2}{B_k N_0} \right), \quad (32)$$

where σ_k is the non-zero singular value that reflects the array gain, the pathloss and the atmospheric losses that can be estimated as given in [40].

Then, the updated optimization problem, is given as

$$\mathcal{P}' : \min_{\mathcal{S}'} \quad \Phi \quad (33a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \hat{C}_{1a} : p_{u,h} + p_{u,s} \leq P_u \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \quad (33b)$$

$$\hat{C}_{1b} : p_{u,h}, p_{u,s} \geq 0 \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \quad (33c)$$

$$C_2 - C_{12},$$

where $\mathcal{S}' = \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}}, \mathbf{P}^{\text{UAV}}, \{\Upsilon_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}, \{\Xi_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{F}\}$, and $\mathbf{P}^{\text{UAV}} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{U \times 2}$ contains the UAV transmit powers to the HAPS and LEO satellite $p_{u,h}$ and $p_{u,s}$ from all UAVs.

IV. PROPOSED LOW-COMPLEXITY TASK OFFLOADING AND RESOURCE ALLOCATION SOLUTION

The optimization problem \mathcal{P}' is non-convex, due to the non-convex terms and cross-terms in the objective function, the constraints, and due to the binary decision variables, which define a non-convex set. Methods exist to handle the binary decision variables which convexify the problem by relaxing these variables and iterating until convergence. However, the parameter tuning and iterative nature of these approaches introduce delays in the system due to algorithm runtime and coordination. This is particularly critical in irregular task generation and real-time resource allocation algorithm execution. With this in mind, we propose a solution to the optimization problem using a one-shot alternating optimization scheme. Each subproblem, or stage, is solved while treating the remaining variables as fixed, and its solution is given as a suboptimal low-complexity algorithm that maintains a low algorithm-runtime delay.

A. Setup and Distribution

The solution to the problem takes the form of a 5-stage algorithm as shown in Fig. 2. In each stage, or step, a minimization problem derived from \mathcal{P}' is solved over a set of variables while keeping the others fixed. The first step is the local IoT computing resources, which can be solved optimally and independently, as it only considers local information at the IoT devices. The second step is the IoT transmit power, which can also be found optimally for each subchannel due to their orthogonality, and it considers an offloading node initialization. The results of these first two steps are then used for the third step, which is the joint offloading and subchannel allocation, which determines the node where the computing of the task occurs, and which subchannel from the IoT device to the UAV is used, needing to initialize the UAV power. After the computing node is established for every task in the system, the corresponding remote resources are optimized in the fourth step, followed by the UAV transmit power in the fifth and final step. This framework and the QTCAJOSA algorithm allow for a choice of computing node that avoids biasing by the initialization of other optimization variables, while maintaining optimality criteria.

Fig. 3 shows the distributed operation of the resource allocation algorithm. Although the algorithm design allows for distribution of the optimization across all the nodes in the system, it also enables the following modes of distribution:

- **Centralized (HAPS):** all of the algorithm stages are run at the HAPS. The algorithm runtime follows a centralized execution, where $k = h$.
- **Distributed (HAPS-UAV):** the algorithm is run at the UAVs with message passing through the HAPS for coordination. The algorithm runtime follows a sequential distributed execution, where $\mathcal{K}_t = \mathcal{U}$ for every t up to algorithm convergence.
- **Distributed (HAPS-UAV-IoT):** the algorithm is run at the UAVs with message passing through the HAPS for coordination, with the exception of the IoT transmit power and computing resources steps, which are run locally at the IoT devices. The algorithm runtime follows a sequential distributed execution, where $\mathcal{K}_1 = \mathcal{K}_2 = \mathcal{I}$ and $\mathcal{K}_t = \mathcal{U}$ for $t > 2$ up to algorithm convergence.

We consider two stages: the algorithm execution and the task offloading. It is assumed that the UAVs and HAPS have the information of available resources at the HAPS and LEO satellite readily available, and that they are aware of the path of the LEO satellite to design the corresponding precoders.

B. Optimization Stages

1) *Step 1 - IoT Computing Resources:* Consider optimization problem \mathcal{P}' , with only the terms related to the IoT computing resources f_i^i , keeping the other variables fixed.

$$\mathcal{P}^{\text{IoT-F}} : \min_{\mathbf{f}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left(1 - \alpha_{i,u}^i \right) \left(\left(f_i^i \right)^2 \varepsilon_E \kappa_i d_i c_i + \frac{1}{f_i^i} \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \right) \quad (34a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } C_3, C_5. \quad (34b)$$

First, the maximum delay constraint can be transformed into a minimum computing resource constraint. Then, this problem

Fig. 2. Optimization framework.

can be decoupled per-task, such that the following problem is solved independently for each task ψ_i

$$\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-F}} : \min_{f_i^i} \left(f_i^i \right)^2 \varepsilon_E \kappa_i d_i c_i + \frac{1}{f_i^i} \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \quad (35a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad F_i^{\min} = \frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \leq f_i^i \leq F_i^{\max}. \quad (35b)$$

For local computing, the maximum delay constraint equals $\tau_i^{\max} = d_i c_i \frac{1}{f_i^i}$, which can be arranged as (35b) to obtain F_i^{\min} . In principle, $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-F}}$ is solved for every task that is locally computed at the corresponding IoT node. However, for the offloading problem we need to consider the optimum possible values if the task is computed at any node in the system. Thus, problem $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-F}}$ is solved for every $i \in \mathcal{I}$, and if the task is finally not computed locally, the resources are reset to zero.

To solve $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-F}}$, note that the objective function is convex over its positive domain. Then, by taking its first derivative and equating it to zero, the optimal point of the objective function is found as

$$f_i^* = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_\tau}{2\varepsilon_E \tau_i^{\max} \kappa_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (36)$$

With this in mind, a simple algorithm to find the optimal local computing resource allocation is as shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: IoT computing resource allocation

- 1 Compute F_i^{\min} and f_i^* ;
 - 2 **if** $F_i^{\min} > F_i^{\max}$ **then**
 - 3 | Set $f_i = F_i^{\max}$
 - 4 **else if** $F_i^{\min} \leq f_i^* \leq F_i^{\max}$ **then**
 - 5 | Set $f_i = f_i^*$
 - 6 **else**
 - 7 | Set $f_i = \text{argmax} \{ \Phi(F_i^{\min}), \Phi(F_i^{\max}) \}$
 - 8 **end**
 - 9 **return** f_i
-

2) *Step 2 - IoT Transmit Power:* Consider optimization problem \mathcal{P}' , with only the terms related to the IoT transmit power $p_{i,u}^b$, keeping the other variables fixed.

$$\mathcal{P}^{\text{IoT-P}} : \min_{\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \left(\frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} + \varepsilon_E d_i \left(\frac{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b p_{i,u}^b}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} \right) \right) \quad (37a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad C_2, C_5, C_{11}. \quad (37b)$$

Given that only one subchannel is chosen at most, and that there is no interference, this problem can be decoupled per task i and subchannel b as

$$\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-PB}} : \min_{p_{i,u}^b} \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{R_{i,u}^b} + \varepsilon_E d_i \left(\frac{p_{i,u}^b}{R_{i,u}^b} \right) \quad (38a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \tau_i \leq \tau_i^{\max} \quad (38b)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,u}^b \leq P_i. \quad (38c)$$

With the same argument as in the previous problem, $\mathcal{P}_i^{\text{IoT-PB}}$ is solved for all task-subchannel pairs. We assume an initialization of the binary decision variables as $\rho_{i,u}^b = 1$ and $\beta_{u,h}^i = \beta_{u,s}^i = 0$, which is to say, the computing is initialized as being performed at the UAV. Considering this, the delay τ_i from Section II-E can be expressed as $\tau_i = d_i c_i \frac{1}{f_i^u} + d_i \frac{1}{R_{i,u}^b}$. After some algebraic manipulation, considering the expression (31), the maximum delay constraint can be written as the following minimum power constraint

$$p_{i,u}^{b,\min} = \frac{B_u N_0}{\|\mathbf{h}_{i,u}^b\|^2} \left(2 \left(B_u \left(\frac{\tau_i^{\max}}{d_i} - \frac{c_i}{f_i^u} \right) \right)^{-1} - 1 \right). \quad (39)$$

The objective function is not convex on $p_{i,u}^b$. However, in the following proposition we prove that it has a single critical point, which is the global minimum.

Proposition 1. *Consider the following function*

$$f(p) = \frac{a}{R} + b \left(\frac{p}{R} \right) = \frac{a + bp}{B \log_2(1 + \gamma p)}. \quad (40)$$

If $B, \gamma > 0$ and $a, b \geq 0$ are constant values, then $f(p)$ has a single critical point, and this critical point is a global minimum for $p > 0$.

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix A. \square

This proposition allows us to obtain the global minimum point of the objective function using numerical methods. In particular, we employ the Newton-Raphson method [41], to obtain the optimal point $p_{i,u}^{b,*}$. Then, similar to the local computing case, the optimal power allocation algorithm is given as in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: IoT Transmit Power Allocation

- 1 Compute $p_{i,u}^{b,\min}$ and $p_{i,u}^{b,*}$;
 - 2 **if** $p_{i,u}^{b,\min} > P_i$ **then**
 - 3 | Set $p_{i,u}^b = P_i$
 - 4 **else if** $p_{i,u}^{b,\min} \leq p_{i,u}^{b,*} \leq P_i$ **then**
 - 5 | Set $p_{i,u}^b = p_{i,u}^{b,*}$
 - 6 **else**
 - 7 | Set $p_{i,u}^b = \text{argmax} \{ \Phi_i(p_{i,u}^{b,\min}), \Phi_i(P_i) \}$
 - 8 **end**
 - 9 **return** $p_{i,u}^b$
-

Fig. 3. Distributed algorithm execution flow.

3) *Step 3 - Quadratic Transform-enabled Computing-Aware Joint Offloading and Subchannel Allocation (QTCAJOSA)*: Consider optimization problem \mathcal{P}' in terms of the subchannel allocation and offloading decision binary variables, while keeping the other variables fixed as

$$\mathcal{P}^{\text{B-D}}: \min_{\substack{\{\Xi_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \\ \{\Upsilon_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b v_{u,b}^i + \sum_{k \in \{h,s\}} \beta_{u,k}^i \left(\frac{\varepsilon_\tau}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \beta_{u,k}^j d_j}{R_{u,k}} + v_k^i \right) \right) \quad (41a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \text{C}_5 - \text{C}_{10}, \quad (41b)$$

where $v_{u,b}^i$, v_h^i and v_s^i are given as

$$v_{u,b}^i = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^u} - \frac{1}{f_i^i} \right) + \varepsilon_E d_i \left(\frac{p_{i,u}^b}{R_{i,u}^b} \right) - \omega_i (f_i^i)^2 \varepsilon_E \kappa_i d_i c_i + \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{R_{i,u}^b}, \quad (42)$$

$$v_h^i = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^h} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right), \quad (43)$$

$$v_s^i = \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^s} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) + \frac{2\varepsilon_\tau \|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{\tau_i^{\max} c}. \quad (44)$$

The objective function could be decoupled across tasks over the $\beta_{u,k}^i$ variables, except for the quadratic cross-terms. To effectively decouple the objective function, we first apply the following algebraic transformation to the quadratic cross-term

$$\frac{\beta_{u,k}^i \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j}{R_{u,k}} = \frac{\left(\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j + \beta_{u,k}^i \right)^2 - \left(\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j - \beta_{u,k}^i \right)^2}{4R_{u,k}}. \quad (45)$$

Then, we apply the quadratic transform (QT) [42] to each of the terms as

$$\frac{\left(\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j \pm \beta_{u,k}^i \right)^2}{R_{u,k}} \Rightarrow 2z_{\pm,i} \left| \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j \pm \beta_{u,k}^i \right| - z_{\pm,i}^2 R_{u,k}, \quad (46)$$

$$z_{\pm,i} = \frac{\left| \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^{j,(n)} \pm \beta_{u,k}^i \right|}{R_{u,k}^{(n)}}. \quad (47)$$

The QT as defined in [42] is proposed for maximization problems, which implies an equivalent alternating optimization formulation. This transformation is not arbitrarily extended to minimization problems. However, it can be shown that for minimization problems, the QT implies a primal-dual method, as in the following proposition.

Proposition 2. Consider the multiple-ratio fractional program

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{A_n(\mathbf{x})}{B_n(\mathbf{x})} \quad (48a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (48b)$$

Applying the QT as in [42], the problem transforms to

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N \left(2z_n \sqrt{A_n(\mathbf{x})} - z_n^2 B_n(\mathbf{x}) \right) \quad (49a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (49b)$$

which is solved iteratively, updating $z_n = \frac{\sqrt{A_n(\mathbf{x})}}{B_n(\mathbf{x})}$ at each iteration for $\forall n = 1, \dots, N$. Then, this iterative process of solving (49) and updating z_n defines a primal-dual method for solving (48).

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix C. \square

Removing the absolute value from the expression, it becomes

$$\frac{\beta_{u,k}^i \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j}{R_{u,k}} = \left(\frac{\beta_{u,k}^{i,(n)}}{R_{u,k}^{(n)}} \right) \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j + \left(\frac{\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^{j,(n)}}{R_{u,k}^{(n)}} \right) \beta_{u,k}^i - \left(\frac{\beta_{u,k}^{i,(n)} \sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^{j,(n)}}{\left(R_{u,k}^{(n)} \right)^2} \right) R_{u,k}. \quad (50)$$

To justify the removal of the absolute value, first assume there exists at least one task $j \in \mathcal{I}$ such that $\beta_{u,k}^j = 1$. Then, since $d_j \geq 1$ for all j , we know that $\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j \geq \beta_{u,k}^i$ and the absolute value can be removed. If, on the other hand, there is no task j for which $\beta_{u,k}^j = 1$, then, assuming that previously allocated tasks cannot be removed from their allocated nodes, (50) also holds.

With this transformation, the objective function for the offloading decision problem can be written as

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b v_{u,b}^i + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u^h} \beta_{u,h}^i v_h^{i,(n)} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u^s} \beta_{u,s}^i v_s^{i,(n)}, \quad (51)$$

where

$$v_k^{i,(n)} = v_k^i + \frac{\varepsilon_\tau d_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{R_{u,k}} + \varepsilon_\tau \frac{1}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} d_j \beta_{u,k}^{j,(n)}}{R_{u,k}^{(n)}} + \varepsilon_\tau d_i \frac{\sum_{j \neq i} \frac{1}{\tau_j^{\max}} \beta_{u,k}^{j,(n)}}{R_{u,k}^{(n)}}, \quad k \in \{h, s\}. \quad (52)$$

Then, the objective function can be decoupled per-task, such that $\beta_{u,k}^i$ is weighted by the impact on the task i of setting the allocation, and by the impact on all of the other already allocated tasks. Then, the optimization problem over the offloading decision variables per UAV u is given as

$$\mathcal{P}_u^{\text{B-D}}: \min_{\Xi_u, \Upsilon_u} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b v_{u,b}^{i,(n)} + \beta_{u,h}^i v_h^{i,(n)} + \beta_{u,s}^i v_s^{i,(n)} \right) \quad (53a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \tau_i \leq \tau_i^{\max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (53b)$$

$$\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (53c)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \rho_{i,u}^b \leq 1 \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (53d)$$

$$\beta_{u,h}^i + \beta_{u,s}^i \leq \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (53e)$$

$$\rho_{i,u}^b \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u, \forall b \in \mathcal{B} \quad (53f)$$

$$\beta_{u,h}^i, \beta_{u,s}^i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u. \quad (53g)$$

With the problem expressed in this form, we can define a greedy algorithm that allocates tasks in rounds, by checking the best possible allocation across all of them one by one. Note that the objective function does not include the added local computing terms. This implies that, for remote computing to be more beneficial than local computing, the resulting objective function should be negative. Otherwise, the objective function would be further penalized.

The solution to this problem depends, particularly, on the initializations of the f_i^k variables. If the total amount of resources F_k^{\max} of remote node k are allocated to all of the tasks in the system for the initialization of the f_i^k variables, it may occur that the share of the remote resources is lower for a task, than the local IoT resources ($f_i^k < f_i^l$). In this scenario the allocation of the task to the remote node will not be realized. This poses an issue, since, even when the initialized remote resources are low, the total amount of resources in remote node k are much larger (F_k^{\max}), with the potential to provide a larger pool of resources to task i . For a large number of tasks in the system, this can be true for every task, and no offloading takes place. In order to address this issue, we propose two measures:

a) *Non-orthogonal Computing Resource Initializations:*

Let $F_{k,u}^{\max}$ be the total resources available at remote node k that are allocated for the tasks handled by UAV u . Consider, then, $F_{k,u}^{\max} = F_k^{\max}$. That is, f_i^k is initialized considering that the serving UAV of i can use all of the resources of remote

node k . In principle, this would result in more resources being advertised than there are available, thus, at the end of each round of the algorithm a tie-break is performed across UAVs, so that the best task across the ones chosen by each UAV is the only one allocated at that round. To implement this, the HAPS coordinates between the UAVs at the end of each round, requiring message passing to coordinate consensus on the resource usage at the HAPS and the LEO satellite. Alternatively, the whole algorithm can run centrally at the HAPS.

b) *Dynamic Computing Resource Initialization:* At each round of the algorithm, the computing resources at each remote node $k \in \mathcal{R}$ are initialized only for the non-allocated tasks. Let $\hat{\mathcal{I}} \subseteq \mathcal{I}$ be the set of tasks not-yet allocated. Then, at the start of each round, the computing resources f_i^k for $i \in \hat{\mathcal{I}}_u$ are initialized considering the optimality criteria from the next optimization step as in (60), for $k \in \mathcal{R}$. This is implemented for the UAV and LEO satellite due to their smaller pools of resources, whereas the HAPS has a larger pool of resources to advertise, so the dynamic initialization of its resources is performed considering all of the tasks, including the already allocated. This avoids an early depletion of resources at the HAPS.

Finally, the algorithm checks the maximum delay feasibility of each new allocation \hat{i} . If $\tau_{\hat{i}} > \tau_{\hat{i}}^{\max}$ and $f_{\hat{i}}^{k,\min} \leq F_k$, it allocates the task and sets $f_{\hat{i}}^k = f_{\hat{i}}^{k,\min}$. Otherwise, if $\tau_{\hat{i}} > \tau_{\hat{i}}^{\max}$ and $f_{\hat{i}}^{k,\min} > F_k$, it does not allocate the task, and it marks \hat{i} so that it cannot be offloaded to k . Then, we present the quadratic transform-enabled computing-aware joint offloading and subchannel allocation (QTCAJOSA) synchronous algorithm in two levels: the coordination and tie-breaking stage at the HAPS in Algorithm 3, and the local UAV execution in Algorithm 4. Furthermore, for simplicity, we present the best local task choice algorithm in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 3: QTCAJOSA HAPS-side

```

1 Send a START message to all UAVs  $u \in \mathcal{U}$  containing
    $\{F_h^{\max}, F_s^{\max}\};;$ 
2 repeat
3   foreach  $u \in \mathcal{U}$  do
4     Receive a message  $\mathcal{M}_u$ ;
5     if  $\mathcal{M}_u$  is an OFFLOAD message then
6       Collect  $\{k_u, b_u, f_{i_u}^{k_u}, v_{i_u}^{k_u}\}$  from  $\mathcal{M}_u$ 
7     end
8     if  $\mathcal{M}_u$  is a FINISH message  $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}$  then
9       Send a CONVERGENCE message to all UAVs
         $u \in \mathcal{U}$ ;
10      return;
11    end
12    foreach  $k \in \{h, s\}$  do
13      if  $|\{v_{i,u}^k\}| > 0$  then
14        Get  $(u_k^*, i_k^*) = \operatorname{argmin}_{(u,i_u)} \{v_{i,u}^k\};$ 
15        Set  $F_k^{\max} := F_k^{\max} - f_{i_k^*}^k$ ;
16      end
17    end
18    Send a SUCCESS message to  $u_h^*$  and  $u_s^*$  containing
         $\{F_h^{\max}, F_s^{\max}\};;$ 
19    Send a FAILURE message to  $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \{u_h^*, u_s^*\}$ 
        containing  $\{F_h^{\max}, F_s^{\max}\};;$ 

```

Algorithm 4: QTCAJOSA UAV-side

```

1 Initialize  $\beta_u^h = \mathbf{0}_{I_u \times 1}$ ,  $\beta_u^s = \mathbf{0}_{I_u \times 1}$  and  $\rho_u = \mathbf{0}_{I_u \times B_u}$ ;
2 Define  $\mathbf{v}_u^h = \mathbf{1}_{I_u \times 1}$ ,  $\mathbf{v}_u^s = \mathbf{1}_{I_u \times 1}$ ,  $\mathbf{v}_u^u = \mathbf{1}_{I_u \times 1}$  and
    $\mathbf{V}_u = \mathbf{1}_{I_u \times B_u}$ ;
3 Initialize  $\hat{\mathcal{I}}_u = \mathcal{I}_u$ ;
4 repeat
5   Receive message  $\mathcal{M}_h$  from HAPS.;
6   switch  $\mathcal{M}_h$  do
7     case START or FAILURE do
8       Update  $\{F_{u,h}^{\max}, F_{u,s}^{\max}\} = \{F_h^{\max}, F_s^{\max}\}$ ;
9     case CONVERGENCE do
10      return;
11    case SUCCESS do
12      Set  $\mathbf{V}_u(i^*, :)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
13      Set  $\mathbf{V}_u(:, b^*)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
14      Set  $\mathbf{v}_u^{k^*}(i^*)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
15      Set  $\hat{\mathcal{I}}_u := \hat{\mathcal{I}}_u \setminus \{i^*\}$ ;
16      Set  $\beta_{u,k^*}^{i^*} = \beta_{i^*,u}^{b^*} = 1$ ;
17      Update  $\{F_{u,h}^{\max}, F_{u,s}^{\max}\} = \{F_h^{\max}, F_s^{\max}\}$ ;
18    end
19    Run Algorithm 5 and obtain  $\{i^*, k^*, b^*, f_{i^*}^{k^*}, v^*\}$ ;
20    if  $v^* == 0$  then
21      Send a FINISH message to the HAPS;
22      Go back to 4;
23    end
24    if  $k^* == u$  then
25      Set  $\mathbf{V}_u(i^*, :)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
26      Set  $\mathbf{V}_u(:, b^*)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
27      Set  $\mathbf{v}_u^u(i^*)$  to  $+\infty$ ;
28      Set  $\hat{\mathcal{I}}_u := \hat{\mathcal{I}}_u \setminus \{i^*\}$ ;
29      Set  $\rho_{i^*,u}^{b^*} = 1$ ,  $\beta_{u,s}^{i^*} = \beta_{u,h}^{i^*} = 0$ ;
30      Update  $F_u^{\max} := F_u^{\max} - f_{i^*}^{k^*}$ ;
31      Send a SKIP message to the HAPS.;
32    else
33      Send a OFFLOAD message to the HAPS containing
         $\{k^*, b^*, f_{i^*}^{k^*}, v^*\}$ ;
34    end
35  until  $\mathcal{M}_h$  is CONVERGENCE;
36 return;

```

Algorithm 5: QTCAJOSA Step

```

1 Initialize  $f_i^k$  for  $k \in \{u, h, s\}$  and  $\forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{I}}_u$ ;
2 Compute  $\mathbf{U}_u$  and vectors as  $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^h$  and  $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^s$ ;
3 Set  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^u := \mathbf{U}_u \odot \mathbf{V}_u \odot \mathbf{v}_u^u$  and  $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^k := \bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^k \odot \mathbf{v}_u^k$  for
    $k \in \{h, s\}$ ;
4 Compute matrices  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k = \mathbf{U}_u + \bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^k$  (column-wise sum) for
    $k \in \{u, h, s\}$ ;
5 Set all elements  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k(i, b)$  such that  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k(i, b) > 0$ , to
    $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k(i, b) := 0$  for  $k \in \{u, h, s\}$ ;
6 Set  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k := \bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k \odot (-\text{sgn}(\bar{\mathbf{u}}_u^k))$  (column-wise) for  $k \in \{h, s\}$ .
   ;
7 Choose  $(i^*, b^*, k^*) = \text{argmin}\{\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k(i, b)\}_{k \in \{u, h, s\}}$ ;
8 if  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^{k^*}(i^*, b^*) \geq 0$  then return  $\{0, 0, 0, 0, 0\}$ ;
9 if  $\tau_{i^*} > \tau_{i^*}^{\max}$  then
10   Set  $f_{i^*}^{k^*} = F_{u,k^*}^{\max}$ ;
11   if  $\tau_{i^*} > \tau_{i^*}^{\max}$  then
12     Set  $\mathbf{v}_u^{k^*}(i^*) = \infty$ ;
13     Go back to 2.;
14   end
15 end
16 return  $\{i^*, k^*, b^*, f_{i^*}^{k^*}, \mathbf{v}_u^{k^*}(i^*)\}$ ;

```

c) *Locally-Infeasible Tasks*: If local computing of a task at its corresponding IoT device is infeasible, it would ideally be offloaded. However, the proposed QTCAJOSA algorithm may not offload tasks if their contribution is not negative, regardless if the tasks are not locally-feasible.

With this in mind, we propose a mechanism for offloading these locally-infeasible tasks in the form of Algorithm 6 that runs prior to QTCAJOSA.

Algorithm 6: Treatment of Locally-Infeasible Tasks

```

1 foreach  $u \in \mathcal{U}$  do
2   Determine the set of locally-infeasible tasks  $\mathcal{I}_u^{\text{li}}$ ;
3   Run a QTCAJOSA step to obtain  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k$  for  $k \in \{u, h, s\}$ ;
4   foreach  $i \in \mathcal{I}_u^{\text{li}}$  do
5     if  $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^k(i, :) \geq 0$  for  $k \in \{u, h, s\}$  then
6       if  $f_u^{i, \min} \leq F_u^{\max}$  then
7         Set  $f_u^i = f_u^{i, \min}$ ;
8         Update  $F_u^{\max} := F_u^{\max} - f_{i^*}^{k^*}$ ;
9         Choose  $b = \text{argmin}_b \bar{\mathbf{U}}_u^u(i, b)$ ;
10        Set  $\rho_{i,u}^b = 1$ ,  $\beta_{u,s}^i = \beta_{u,h}^i = 0$ ;
11        Set  $\mathcal{I}_u := \mathcal{I}_u \setminus \{i\}$ ;
12      end
13    else
14      Include  $i$  in  $\mathcal{I}_u^{\text{liP}}$ ;
15    end
16  end
17 end
18 Run QTCAJOSA algorithm with the following
   considerations: Computing resources initializations consider
    $\{\mathcal{I}_u\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}$ , but offloading only possible for tasks in  $\mathcal{I}_u^{\text{liP}}$ ;
19 Run QTCAJOSA normally for the remaining tasks;

```

The algorithm first considers the locally-infeasible tasks that do not lower the objective function, and allocates the minimum needed computing resources at the local UAV. Then, it runs the QTCAJOSA algorithm for all the locally-infeasible tasks that have offloading options that lower the objective function. During this process, only the locally-infeasible tasks are allocated, therefore, the remote computing resources are initialized considering all the non-allocated tasks. This is done to prevent all of the resources from being depleted before proceeding to the rest of the tasks.

4) *Step 4 - Remote Computing Resources*: Consider optimization problem \mathcal{P}' in terms of the remote computing resources, while keeping the other variables fixed, as

$$\mathcal{P}^{\text{R-F}} : \min_{\mathbf{F}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left(\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\tau} d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) \right) \right) \quad (54a)$$

$$+ \sum_{k \in \{h, s\}} \beta_{u,k}^i \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\tau} d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \left(\frac{1}{f_i^k} - \frac{1}{f_i^u} \right) \right) \quad (54b)$$

s.t. C_4, C_5, C_{12} .

This problem can be decoupled per remote node, and the maximum delay constraint can be transformed into a minimum computing resources constraint. Defining \mathcal{I}^k as the set of tasks computed in remote node k , each subproblem can be written as

$$\mathcal{P}_k^{\text{R-F}} : \min_{\{f_i^k\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} \frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{f_i^k} \quad (55a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} f_i^k \leq F_k^{\max} \quad (55b)$$

$$f_i^k \geq \frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max} - \tau_{i \rightarrow k}} = f_i^{k, \min} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k \quad (55c)$$

$$f_i^k \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k, \quad (55d)$$

where $\tau_{i \rightarrow k}$ represents the delay of task ψ_i up to arriving at node k , and is given as

$$\tau_{i \rightarrow u} = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b}, \quad (56)$$

$$\tau_{i \rightarrow h} = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} + \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u^h} d_j}{R_{u,h}}, \quad (57)$$

$$\tau_{i \rightarrow s} = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_{i,u}^b R_{i,u}^b} + \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u^s} d_j}{R_{u,s}} + \frac{2\|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{c}, \quad (58)$$

where \mathcal{I}_u^k is the set of tasks offloaded from UAV u to $k \in \{h, s\}$. The problem $\mathcal{P}_k^{\text{R-F}}$ is convex, therefore, it can be solved efficiently with iterative numerical methods. Moreover, a simple, closed form algorithm can be designed to solve the problem. To this end, let us first introduce the following proposition.

Proposition 3. Consider the following convex optimization problem

$$\min_{\{f_i^k\}_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} \frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max} f_i^k} \quad (59a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} f_i^k \leq F_k^{\max} \quad (59b)$$

$$f_i^k \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k. \quad (59c)$$

It has a closed-form solution given as

$$f_i^{k,*} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}}}}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} \sqrt{\frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}}}} F_k^{\max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k. \quad (60)$$

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix B. \square

Given that the solution in (60) does not account for the constraint on the minimum resources, it needs to be checked manually. Thus, if a task is not feasible at the optimal point, the algorithm will assign their required minimum resources, if possible. The remote computing resources allocation algorithm is presented in Algorithm 7.

5) *Step 5 - UAV Transmit Power:* With some algebraic manipulation, we can write the optimization problem \mathcal{P}' in terms of the UAV transmission power variables, while keeping the other variables fixed, as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}^{\text{PU}} : \quad & \min_{\mathbf{P}^{\text{UAV}}} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{k \in \{h, s\}} \left(\frac{1}{R_{u,k}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,k}^i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\varepsilon_{\tau} d_j}{\tau_i^{\max}} \beta_{u,k}^j \right) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & C_{1a}, C_{1b}, C_5. \end{aligned} \quad (61a)$$

Given the orthogonal access from the UAVs to the HAPS and the LEO satellite, this problem can be decoupled per UAV as

$$\mathcal{P}_u^{\text{PU}} : \quad \min_{p_{u,h}, p_{u,s}} \sum_{k \in \{h, s\}} \left(\frac{1}{R_{u,k}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \beta_{u,k}^i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u} \frac{\varepsilon_{\tau} d_j}{\tau_i^{\max}} \beta_{u,k}^j \right) \quad (62a)$$

Algorithm 7: Remote computing resources allocation

```

1 For the set of tasks  $\hat{\mathcal{I}}^k$  for which  $\tau_{i \rightarrow k} > \tau_i^{\max}$ , remove
  them from  $\mathcal{I}^k$  as  $\mathcal{I}^k := \mathcal{I}^k \setminus \hat{\mathcal{I}}^k$ ;
2 repeat
3   foreach  $i \in \mathcal{I}^k$  do Compute  $f_i^{k,*}$ ;
4   if  $f_i^{k,*} \geq f_i^{k, \min} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k$  then
5      $f_i^k := f_i^{k,*} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}^k$ ;
6     return
7   Populate  $\hat{\mathcal{I}}^k$  with tasks  $i$  such that  $f_i^{k,*} < f_i^{k, \min}$ ;
8   For  $\hat{i} = \text{argmax}_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{I}}^k} \{f_i^{k, \min} - f_i^{k,*}\}$ , assign
      $f_{\hat{i}}^k = f_{\hat{i}}^{k, \min}$ ;
9   Set  $F_{k,u}^{\max} := F_{k,u}^{\max} - f_{\hat{i}}^k$ ;
10  if  $F_{k,u}^{\max} < 0$  then
11     $F_{k,u}^{\max} := F_{k,u}^{\max} + f_{\hat{i}}^k$ ;
12     $f_{\hat{i}}^k := 0$ ;
13     $\mathcal{I}^k := \mathcal{I}^k \setminus \{\hat{i}\}$ 
14 until  $|\mathcal{I}^k| = 1$ ;
15  $f_i^k := F_k^{\max}$ ;
16 return;
```

$$\text{s.t.} \quad p_{u,h} + p_{u,s} \leq P_u \quad (62b)$$

$$\tau_i \leq \tau_i^{\max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_u \quad (62c)$$

$$p_{u,h}, p_{u,s} \geq 0. \quad (62d)$$

The constraint (62c) can be formulated as a minimum power constraint expressed as

$$p_{u,k}^{\min} = \frac{B_k N_0}{\sigma_k^2} \left(2 \left(\frac{B_k}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u^k} d_j} \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u^k} \{\tau_i^{\max} - \hat{\tau}_k^i\} \right)^{-1} - 1 \right), \quad (63)$$

where $\hat{\tau}_h^i = d_i \frac{1}{R_{i,u}^{b_i}} + d_i c_i \frac{1}{f_i^k}$ and $\hat{\tau}_s^i = d_i \frac{1}{R_{i,u}^{b_i}} + d_i c_i \frac{1}{f_i^s} + \frac{2\|\mathbf{r}_s - \mathbf{r}_u\|_2}{c}$. This is a convex optimization problem that can be solved with a simple low-complexity algorithm. To show this, let us first consider the following proposition.

Proposition 4. The solution that minimizes the objective function (62a), while accounting for the maximum power constraint (62b) is given by finding the value of $p_{u,h}$ that fulfills the following equation

$$\left(\frac{1 + \zeta_h p_{u,h}}{1 + \zeta_s (P_u - p_{u,h})} \right) \left(\frac{\log(1 + \zeta_h p_{u,h})}{\log(1 + \zeta_s (P_u - p_{u,h}))} \right)^2 = \frac{\zeta_{u,h} a_h B_s}{\zeta_{u,s} a_s B_h}, \quad (64)$$

$$\text{where } a_k = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_u} \frac{\beta_{u,k}^i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{I}_u} d_j \beta_{u,k}^j \text{ and } \zeta_k = \frac{\sigma_k^2}{B_k N_0}.$$

Proof. The proof is provided in Appendix D. \square

A bisection-based algorithm is presented in Algorithm 8, which is designed to solve (64), while also accounting for the maximum delay constraints. Note that the bisection takes N_{UP} steps to converge, which can be adjusted depending on the precision needed ϵ as $N_{\text{UP}} \geq \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(P_u - (p_{u,h}^{\min} + p_{u,s}^{\min}) \right) \right)$. This number can be set dynamically, but we can also further find an upper bound as $N_{\text{UP}} \geq \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} P_u \right)$. Then, to obtain a precision relative to the maximum UAV power as $\epsilon = 10^{-r} P_u$, the number of iterations needed to guarantee it is $N_{\text{UP}} = \left\lceil \frac{r}{\log_{10}(2)} \right\rceil$.

Algorithm 8: UAV Power Allocation

```

1 if  $p_{u,h}^{\min} > P_u$  and  $p_{u,s}^{\min} \leq P_u$  then
2   | Set  $p_{u,h} := 1 - p_{u,s}^{\min}$  and  $p_{u,s} := p_{u,s}^{\min}$ . return;
3 if  $p_{u,h}^{\min} \leq P_u$  and  $p_{u,s}^{\min} > P_u$  then
4   | Set  $p_{u,h} := p_{u,h}^{\min}$  and  $p_{u,s} := 1 - p_{u,h}^{\min}$ . return;
5 if  $p_{u,h}^{\min} > P_u$  and  $p_{u,s}^{\min} > P_u$  then
6   | Set
7     |  $p_{u,h} := \left( \frac{p_{u,h}^{\min}}{p_{u,h}^{\min} + p_{u,s}^{\min}} \right) P_u$  and  $p_{u,s} := \left( \frac{p_{u,s}^{\min}}{p_{u,h}^{\min} + p_{u,s}^{\min}} \right) P_u$ ;
8   | return;
9 if  $p_{u,h}^{\min} + p_{u,s}^{\min} > P_u$  then
10  | Set  $p_{u,h}^h := p_{u,h}^{\min}$ ;  $p_{u,s}^h := 1 - p_{u,h}^{\min}$ ;  $p_{u,h}^s := 1 - p_{u,s}^{\min}$ ;
11  |  $p_{u,s}^s := p_{u,s}^{\min}$ ;
12  |  $\Phi^h := \frac{a_h}{R_{u,h}(p_{u,h}^h)} + \frac{a_s}{R_{u,s}(p_{u,s}^h)}$ ;
13  |  $\Phi^s := \frac{a_h}{R_{u,h}(p_{u,h}^s)} + \frac{a_s}{R_{u,s}(p_{u,s}^s)}$ ;
14  | if  $\Phi^h \leq \Phi^s$  then
15  |   | Set  $p_{u,h} := p_{u,h}^h$  and  $p_{u,s} := p_{u,s}^h$ ;
16  |   | else
17  |     | Set  $p_{u,h} := p_{u,h}^s$  and  $p_{u,s} := p_{u,s}^s$ ;
18  |   | end
19  | return;
20 Set  $p_{u,h}^{\min} := p_{u,h}^{\min}$  and  $p_{u,s}^{\max} := P_u - p_{u,h}^{\min}$ ;
21 Set  $\zeta := \frac{\gamma_{u,h} a_h B_s}{\gamma_{u,s} a_s B_h}$ ;
22 for  $n = 1 : N_{UP}$  do
23   | Set  $p = \frac{p_{u,h}^{\min} + p_{u,s}^{\max}}{2}$ ;
24   | Compute  $\eta := \left( \frac{1 + \zeta_h p}{1 + \zeta_s (P_u - p)} \right) \left( \frac{\log(1 + \zeta_h p)}{\log(1 + \zeta_s (P_u - p))} \right)^2$ ;
25   | if  $\eta > \zeta$  then
26   |   |  $p_{u,h}^{\max} := p$ ;
27   |   | else
28   |     |  $p_{u,h}^{\min} := p$ ;
29   |   | end
30 end
31 Set  $p_{u,h} := p$  and  $p_{u,s} := P_u - p$ ;
32 return;

```

C. Operation Count

To determine the algorithm execution time, we need to determine the number of cycles needed to execute it. To do this, we perform a counting of the operations needed for each of the algorithms exposed previously. For simplicity, we assume that additions, multiplications and divisions count as elementary operations. The amount of elementary operations involved in other familiar functions, such as exponentiation and logarithms, depend on factors such as the method used and the precision required. Thus, for simplicity, and to avoid considering a specific methodology or architecture, we assume that these operations take 10 elementary operations. Furthermore, for iterative algorithms, the amount of total operations performed cannot be previously determined, but an upper bound can be established by observation, or by setting a maximum number of iterations, which can be derived by the behavior of the algorithm, or by common values observed in the simulations.

Under these assumptions, Table III shows an upper bound of the total number of operations per optimization stage for each level of distribution.

D. Convergence Analysis

The presented 5-stage algorithm can be seen as a one-shot alternating optimization algorithm with a single iteration per-

formed. This is done in line with the objective of maintaining low-complexity, and thus avoiding the added complexity of performing several iterations over each of the steps, some of which already iterate over their variables.

The local resource allocation algorithm needs only to be solved once, as its solution is independent of any other parameters in the system. The IoT power allocation algorithm is initialized considering computing at the UAV, which enables further offloading to the HAPS or LEO if these are better alternatives. The offloading problem considers a dynamic resource allocation initialization, which removes its dependence of its initialization, and, in turn, by setting the offloading decisions, it biases the computing resource allocation. Finally, the UAV transmit power follows this optimal allocation.

Let $\Phi^{(1)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{f}\})$ be the objective function after solving problem (35). By Algorithm 1, the optimal \mathbf{f} values are given in closed form, independent of any other variable $\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{f}\}$. As such, the optimal \mathbf{f} values serve as reference values to choose the offloading destination of the task. Let $\Phi^{(2)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}}\})$ be the objective function after solving problem (37). This problem is solved independently for every element of \mathbf{P}^{IoT} and, for the fixed \mathbf{f} values, it is guaranteed that $\Phi^{(2)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{IoT}}\}) \leq \Phi^{(1)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{f}\})$. At each step t of the QTCAJOSA algorithm, define $\Phi_t^{(3)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\{\rho_{i_t,u}^b\}, \{\beta_{u,k}^{i_t}\}, \{f_{i_t}^k\}\})$, which reflects the value of the objective function after step t , in which node i_t is allocated. By the derivation of the QTCAJOSA algorithm, a node is allocated if and only if such allocation lowers the objective function value, so it is guaranteed that $\Phi_t^{(3)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\{\rho_{i_t,u}^b\}, \{\beta_{u,k}^{i_t}\}, \{f_{i_t}^k\}\}) \leq \Phi_{t-1}^{(3)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\{\rho_{i_{t-1},u}^b\}, \{\beta_{u,k}^{i_{t-1}}\}, \{f_{i_{t-1}}^k\}\})$ up to the final step $t = T \leq I$.

While QTCAJOSA checks for maximum delay feasibility of every new allocated task, it does not check over all of the already allocated tasks to avoid increasing the complexity of the algorithm by orders of magnitude. Nevertheless, the computing resource allocation problem (54) checks for the feasibility of the tasks and drops any non-feasible task to be computed at the corresponding UAV. In that sense, it can be guaranteed that $\Phi^{(4)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{F}\}) \leq \Phi_1^{(3)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\{\rho_{i_1,u}^b\}, \{\beta_{u,k}^{i_1}\}, \{f_{i_1}^k\}\})$ where $\Phi^{(4)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{F}\})$ is the objective function after solving the resource allocation problem. However, since the computing resource solution is feasible, it can be guaranteed that $\Phi^{(4)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{F}\}) \leq \Phi_t^{(3)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\{\rho_{i_t,u}^b\}, \{\beta_{u,k}^{i_t}\}, \{f_{i_t}^k\}\}) \delta_t^{\text{feas}} \quad \forall t = 0, \dots, T$, where δ_t^{feas} equals 1 if the allocation so far is feasible, and infinity if it is not feasible for some allocated task. Finally, let $\Phi^{(5)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{UAV}}\})$ be the objective function value after the UAV power allocation (61). Given that the UAV power allocation problem is solved independently at each UAV and that the previous solution is feasible, it is guaranteed that $\Phi^{(5)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{P}^{\text{UAV}}\}) \leq \Phi^{(4)}(\mathcal{S} \setminus \{\mathbf{F}\})$.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

As per 3GPP recommendations [43], the carrier frequency for the UAV-LEO/HAPS link is in the Ka band, chosen as 28GHz and 28.7GHz, with bandwidths $B_s = 200\text{MHz}$ and

TABLE III
OPERATION COUNT FOR ALGORITHMS

	Centralized (HAPS)	Distributed (HAPS-UAV)	Distributed (HAPS-UAV-IoT)
IoT Computing Resources	$26I$	$26I_u$	26
IoT Transmit Power	$390IB$	$390I_uB$	$390B$
QTCAJOSA	$I(6(I^2) + 6IB + 100I + 3B + 100)$	$I(6(I_u^2) + 6I_uB + 100I_u + 3B + 100)$	
Remote Computing Resources	$(U + 2)(2(I_u^2) + 24I_u + 15)$	$3(2(I_u^2) + 24I_u + 15)$	
UAV Transmit Power	$U \left(18I_u + 38 + 36 \frac{r}{\log_{10}(2)} \right)$	$18I_u + 38 + 36 \frac{r}{\log_{10}(2)}$	

TABLE IV
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

U	25	B	14
I_u	17	B_u	1.4 MHz
\mathbf{r}_h	[0, 0, 20] km	B_h	100 MHz
\mathbf{r}_s	[0, 0, 500] km	B_s	200 MHz
d_i	10 Mbits	A_1	5
c_i	100 cycles/bit	A_2	$\frac{2}{\pi} \log(3)$
τ_i^{\max}	30 s	η_{LoS}	0.1
F_i^{\max}	64 MHz	η_{NLoS}	21
F_u^{\max}	1 GHz	ψ	2
F_h^{\max}	10 GHz	ω	0.429
F_s^{\max}	1 GHz	ϱ	4.88
ε_τ	1	η_u	1×10^{-9}
c_{op}	1	κ_i	1×10^{-27}

Fig. 4. Total IoT energy spent and task delay of all of the tasks for varying ε_τ and τ_i^{\max} values.

$B_h = 100\text{MHz}$. For the IoT-UAV access, we assume LTE-M enabled IoT devices working in LTE channel [44], thus, we choose a subchannel bandwidth of $B_u = 1.4\text{MHz}$ and $B = 14$ subchannels over the carrier at 2.1GHz. The altitude of the UAVs is taken as $z_u = 100\text{m}$ for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$, chosen according to the maximum allowable altitude of 120m by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) [45]. We consider a LEO satellite at an altitude of $z_s = 500\text{km}$, and a HAPS at an altitude of $z_h = 20\text{km}$, both at horizontal coordinates [0, 0] at the time of algorithm execution. We consider clear-sky conditions such that $G_{u,h} = G_{u,s} = 1$. Table IV shows the parameters used in the forthcoming simulations, unless stated otherwise.

Fig. 4 shows the total energy and delay obtained for varying values of ε_τ and τ_i^{\max} . As expected, smaller ε_τ values imply larger ε_E values, minimizing the energy and causing a trade-

Fig. 5. Relative delay residual CDF for weighted and non-weighted delay.

off in which the delay is maximized. Similarly, for ε_τ close to 1, the priority of the problem is to minimize the delay, which decreases as the energy is increased as a trade-off.

Furthermore, the maximum task delay has different effects on the delay and the energy. If the delay is less constrained (higher τ_i^{\max}) for smaller ε_τ , less resources are utilized to compute the task to save energy, increasing the delay to the maximum allowable. Thus, for energy priority, higher values of τ_i^{\max} cause the delay to approach τ_i^{\max} , increasing the total delay linearly. For ε_τ closer to 1, the priority is to minimize the delay, thus, the maximum task delay does not impact the results, as the expected output already strictly meets the constraint.

When ε_τ is close to 1, the resulting offloading profile is the same for every τ_i^{\max} and the power used for transmission is the same. Energy is not considered in the optimization, thus, the energy spent is kept the same. For ε_τ closer to 0, the offloading profile is also the same and the main source of energy expenditure is due to transmission. On this end, more constrained delays (lower τ_i^{\max}) imply transmission with higher power to achieve higher rates and meet the constraints. However, the difference is not large due to the inverse exponential relation to the minimum power required (see Eq.(39)).

To assess the impact of the weighting of the delay by the maximum allowable delay, consider Fig. 5. For this figure, 100 experiments were simulated in which tasks have maximum delays taken from a uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}([1, 100])$ for values of computing density of $c_i = [50, 100, 200]$. The metric shown is the residual delay relative to the maximum delay, named for convenience as relative delay residual. This provides insight into how far from the maximum delay a task is: a value closer

Fig. 6. Proportion of tasks offloaded in the system over computing density of the tasks.

to 0 implies that the actual delay is very close to its maximum delay, while a value closer to 1 implies that the actual delay is very small relative to the maximum delay.

Fig. 5 shows the distribution of the relative delay residual for the experiments with and without the maximum delay weighting. It can be clearly seen that the weighting causes a narrower distribution closer to 1, while the non-weighted curves show a more spread-out distribution, where higher values of computing density result in tasks computed in a larger time due to the increased computing time. This means that, using the weighting, the tasks have a much more similar relative delay residual, which implies a higher level of fairness irrespective of their maximum delays. It also shows that using the maximum delay weighting results in fewer amount of infeasible tasks, due to the unbiasing at the time of deciding which task to offload.

Regarding where tasks are offloaded, one of the main factors that influences if tasks are computed locally or remotely is the task computing density, given that the task density increases the computing delay and energy, but not the transmit delay and energy. To illustrate this, Fig. 6 shows the proportion of tasks offloaded, and where they are computed for varying computing density of the tasks c_i in cycles per bit.

Fig. 6 also shows the operation of the QTCAJOSA algorithm. The tasks are initially offloaded to the HAPS, since it has the most amount of computing resources. However, after $c_i = 5$ there are enough tasks offloaded to the HAPS, such that the computing resources at the UAV and LEO satellite are initialized to the fewer, non-allocated tasks. This makes offloading to the UAV and to the LEO satellite more advantageous, given that their initialized computing resources are relatively higher per task. Particularly, UAVs have dedicated resources for their local tasks, which causes most of the tasks to be offloaded to them.

We can also see that the resources of the LEO satellite are allocated to a small proportion of the nodes in the system, which is to be expected due to its resources being the same as the UAV, but they are shared across all tasks in the system with the added propagation delay. However, the presence of the LEO satellite can be beneficial when the service areas are too broad and the nodes fall outside the coverage area of the

Fig. 7. Proportion of tasks offloaded in the system over maximum ground distance from the origin of the ground nodes.

HAPS.

Fig. 7 shows the proportion of tasks offloaded, and where they are computed for varying values of d_{\max} , which is the maximum ground distance of the IoT devices from the $[0, 0]$ coordinate. This figure illustrates the importance of the UAVs and LEO satellite as MEC servers. If the distance of the IoT devices is too large, their serving UAVs smoothly fall outside the coverage area of the HAPS, decreasing the amount of tasks offloaded to it. However, since the UAVs are still present and within the coverage area of the LEO satellite, the tasks can be offloaded to these nodes.

Fig. 8. Average task delay over computing density of the tasks for different benchmarks.

In Fig. 8, we compare the performance of the QTCAJOSA algorithm against two state-of-the-art benchmarks for the offloading problem: an iterative successive convex approximation (SCA) approach over a relaxed offloading problem with proximity constraints, and a block successive upper bound minimization (BSUM) approach with proximity constraints as in [18]. Furthermore, the figure shows the result from considering and not considering the algorithm runtime in the optimization over varying c_i .

At first glance, it is apparent that both the SCA and BSUM benchmarks, by virtue of being iterative algorithms, exhibit a much larger algorithm runtime delay, given that stages 2 through 5 of the optimization framework are computed until convergence for relaxed offloading and subchannel alloca-

Fig. 9. Total device energy spent of all of the IoT devices over UAV computing resources for different algorithm architectures.

tion variables. Whereas, the algorithm runtime consideration increases only slightly the delay obtained by the proposed QTCAJOSA, due to its low-complexity. It is interesting to note that, without considering the algorithm runtime, QTCAJOSA obtains results very close to the SCA benchmark for high c_i values, which are when the tasks are more incentivized to offload, while for low c_i values, with fewer incentives for offloading, QTCAJOSA outperforms the benchmarks. On the other hand the BSUM benchmark is always worse, due to it considering an upper bound for the offloading decisions, and thus making a decision always based on a pessimistic worst-case scenario. It is clear that for real-time decision making of sporadically-generated data, QTCAJOSA outperforms the benchmarks.

Fig. 9 shows the total energy obtained by the proposed algorithm run at different modes of distribution, for varying values of the computing resources available at the UAV F_u^{\max} , setting $\varepsilon_E = 1$. The benchmarks of independent resources consider an orthogonal initialization of the remote computing resources at the UAVs, keeping a fixed $F_{u,k}^{\max}$ value throughout. This allows these cases to run independently at each UAV for their serving IoT devices. The independent resources central UAV benchmark considers central algorithm execution with $k = u$ at each UAV, while the corresponding UAV-IoT benchmark considers sequential distributed execution with $\mathcal{K}_1 = \mathcal{K}_2 = \mathcal{I}_u$ and $\mathcal{K}_t = \{u\}$ for $t > 2$, for each cluster independently.

This figure shows the impact of the algorithm execution delay on the energy spent by the IoT devices. For the cases in which the algorithm is partially executed at the UAVs, when the computing resources at the UAVs are low, the algorithm execution delay will be higher. This further constraints the maximum task delays, which forces the IoT nodes to consume all their power in either offloading or local computing. However, if the resources at the UAV are too low, this eventually causes the tasks to be locally infeasible, forcing the IoT devices to offload to the UAV. However, if the computing resources at the UAV are too low, the tasks become infeasible to compute there as well. This explains the early behavior in this figure.

On the other hand, the curves for independent resources have better performance given that their algorithm runtime

Fig. 10. Total delay of all of the tasks over IoT computing resources for different available nodes in the system.

is lower, due to the lower number of operations of handling only local tasks. The better performance in most regions of this graph is given by the centralized approach at the HAPS, given that it has enough resources to efficiently compute the algorithm. For very large UAV computing resources, the best solution in any case is to compute everything at the UAV with minimal IoT transmit power, which explains the sudden drop around the 10^9 point. In this case, the performance of the centralized configuration is only slightly worse than that of the distributed configurations.

The corresponding delay curves are not shown, as for $\varepsilon_\tau = 0$, all of the delay curves will be constant at the sum maximum delay of all the tasks. This occurs because of the tradeoff between energy and delay seen in Fig. 4, which suggest that, for only energy minimization, the solution sets the delays as high as possible, to allow for the maximum decrease in the energy spent by the IoT devices.

Fig. 10 shows the total delay obtained by the algorithm run at different configurations of available nodes in the system, for varying values of the computing resources available at the IoT devices F_i^{\max} . In general, increasing the computing resources at any of the computing nodes allows for a faster execution of the task by lowering the computing delay, as can be seen in (14). In consequence, for $\varepsilon_\tau > 0$, increasing the computing resources at a given computing node increases the incentive for executing the task at that node. Thus, a larger pool of resources at any node will maintain or decrease the delay. In the left-most portion of the graph the local computing resources at the IoT devices is low enough such that the solution is always to offload every task. In particular, the configurations in which some of the algorithm processing is performed at the IoT nodes, perform the worst, since their resulting algorithm runtime delays are larger. Moreover, for the region of the figure that has small local resources, the best algorithms are the ones that give the most optimal solutions, which is the case for the central resources configuration, in particular the ones distributed only to the UAVs or centralized at the HAPS.

For larger values of local IoT computing resources, the solution is to always perform local computing. This is true for all of the configurations, thus, the ones that exhibit a

Fig. 11. Total delay of all of the tasks over task size for different available nodes in the system under delay minimization ($\varepsilon_\tau = 1$).

better performance are the ones in which the algorithm runtime delay is smaller, which is the case of independent resources. This clearly shows two distinct regions: the leftmost region that is optimality-dominated, and the right-most region that is complexity-dominated.

In contrast, the case for $\varepsilon_\tau = 0$ is not plotted, since, for the simulation parameters considered, offloading always takes place to the UAV for any value of F_i^{\max} . This occurs because, for feasible IoT task processing, the preference for offloading does not depend on the resources at the IoT device, since they are given optimally as the least amount of resources possible as in (35b). And, for infeasible processing, the tasks will always get offloaded to the UAV.

Fig. 11 shows the total delay obtained by the algorithm run at different configurations of available nodes in the system, for varying values of the size of the tasks in bits d_i . The benchmarks indicate the algorithm running in a system without a specific set of nodes, either without having available the LEO satellite, the HAPS, the computing at the UAVs, or with only local computing at the IoT devices. It also shows a benchmark in which the QTCAJOSA algorithm does not consider an adaptive computing resource initialization at each step, but rather performs a single initialization at the beginning. For this figure, the computing resources at the IoT device and the UAVs are set to values such that the computing of their corresponding tasks are feasible. For the no HAPS case, the algorithm follows centralized execution with $k = s$.

There are two visible regions in this plot. The left-most region is the region with low task size, where the time to compute a task is also very low, which causes the task computing delay to fall below the level of the algorithm execution delay. Thus, this is a complexity-dominated region, in which the algorithms that perform the best are the ones that have low algorithm execution delay (least amount of operations). In this region, the best performing curve is the one with only local computing, followed by the non-adaptive algorithm, and the no LEO (only HAPS) due to the smaller number of operations, and the worst is the no HAPS (only LEO) due to the large propagation time for coordination.

In the right-most region of the plot, the task sizes are large enough such that the algorithm execution time does not

contribute meaningfully to the total delay compared to the task computing and offloading times. This is an optimality-dominated region, in which the adaptive algorithm outperforms the non-adaptive algorithm considering the same nodes. In this region, the proposed solution improves on the total delay by 26.5% from the only IoT scenario, by 17.7% from the no HAPS scenario, by 16.1% from the no UAV scenario, by 12.4% from the non-adaptive scenario and by 1.2% from the no LEO scenario.

Fig. 12. Total energy spent of all IoT devices and proportion of feasible tasks for varying d_i , considering various modes of offloading.

To contrast this with energy minimization, Fig. 12 shows the total energy expenditure across the IoT devices for $\varepsilon_\tau = 0$. The figure is shown varying task size d_i under the proposed algorithm, a non-adaptive algorithm, for only IoT local computing, with only offloading and also showing the proportion of feasible tasks obtained by each scenario.

By simple inspection it can be seen that, for energy minimization, local computing is preferable under very low and very large d_i values, with a range of values for which offloading is preferable (roughly from 100Kbs to 10Mbs). The proposed solution follows the optimal allocation earlier than the non-adaptive algorithm, and also with better results for larger values of d_i . Moreover, the proposed algorithm achieves lower energy expenditure and a higher proportion of feasible tasks than total local computing or total offloading. This occurs because the total offloading scenario considers a minimum power as defined in (39), which only considers the resources at the UAV, which suggests that the inclusion of the other NTN nodes provide a better performance in terms of energy, and in terms of feasibility.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work studied the resource allocation problem for task offloading of tasks generated irregularly by clusters of IoT devices, to a NTN consisting of dedicated UAVs per cluster, a common HAPS and a common LEO satellite. For the allocation of IoT-UAV subchannels, transmit power, computing resources and offloading nodes, a 5-step one-shot BCD low-complexity algorithm was designed and implemented over different modes of distribution. The algorithm minimizes a weighted sum of total weighted task delay and total IoT energy

consumption. The algorithm runtime delay was considered, accounting for the number of operations involved in the algorithms.

With extensive simulations, the performance of the algorithm was compared to a simpler non-adaptive algorithm, to architectures with fewer nodes in the system, and to state-of-the-art benchmarks. It was found that the baseline algorithm considering all the proposed nodes in the architecture outperformed the benchmarks under regions where the algorithm runtime was negligible, but also, that simpler algorithms and architectures have better performance where either the task execution delay is small compared to the algorithm execution delay, or if the solution is self-evident by simple inspection.

The results obtained by this work suggest that complex algorithms for resource allocation may not be more optimal in real-time decision making than simpler suboptimal heuristics due to the runtime delay incurred. It also suggests that the three types of NTN nodes considered serve a distinct purpose: the UAVs as dedicated resource pools and local coordinators, the HAPS as an ample common pool of resources and global coordinator, and the LEO satellite as a large-coverage common resource pool.

Future research directions may consider the use of the time domain within the optimization, as well as the modeling of queues at each node. Another future direction includes the consideration of partial offloading, the trajectory design of the UAVs, the choice of MEC servers across several LEO satellites or HAPS, as well as the possibility of offloading tasks between UAVs.

APPENDIX A

EXISTENCE OF GLOBAL MINIMUM FOR IOT POWER OBJECTIVE FUNCTION

We can find the critical points of (40) by derivating this function and equaling it to zero. Following this, and assuming constants $B, \gamma > 0$ we obtain the following expression for the critical points p^* :

$$b(1 + \gamma p^*) \log(1 + \gamma p^*) = \gamma(a + bp^*) \quad (65)$$

Then, by taking the second derivative of $f(p)$ and obtaining the condition for convexity, which is $\frac{d^2 f(p)}{dp^2} \geq 0$, after some arithmetic manipulation we obtain the condition:

$$2\gamma(a + bp) + \gamma(a + bp) \log(1 + \gamma p) - 2b(1 + \gamma p) \log(1 + \gamma p) \geq 0 \quad (66)$$

Then, we analyze the convexity of the function at the critical points by replacing (65) into (66). We obtain the condition

$$\gamma(a + bp^*) \log(1 + \gamma p^*) \geq 0 \quad (67)$$

which is true for any non-negative value of p^* , and a, b . With this we infer that any critical point of $f(p)$ is a local minimum. Furthermore, since $f(p)$ is smooth for positive $p > 0$, then this can only be true if there exists only one critical point, which is also the global minimum. From this we can further infer that the function is monotonic to the left and to the right of the global minimum p^* .

APPENDIX B

OPTIMAL REMOTE RESOURCE ALLOCATION

We write the partial Lagrangian considering the first constraint as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{f}, \lambda) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} \frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}} \frac{1}{f_i^k} + \lambda \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} f_i^k - F_{k,u}^{\max} \right) \quad (68)$$

Taking the derivative of the partial Lagrangian with respect to f_i^k and equaling to zero we obtain

$$f_i^k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \sqrt{\frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}}} \quad (69)$$

Replacing this expression in constraint (59b) and working out the algebra, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} = \frac{F_{k,u}^{\max}}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}^k} \sqrt{\frac{d_i c_i}{\tau_i^{\max}}}} \quad (70)$$

Replacing in (69), the objective function optimal is given as in (60).

APPENDIX C

QT FOR MINIMIZATION PROBLEMS

Consider the following transformation of problem (48):

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}} \quad & \sum_i \frac{a_i^2}{b_i} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \\ & A_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq a_i^2 \quad \forall i \\ & B_i(\mathbf{x}) \geq b_i \quad \forall i \\ & b_i \geq 0 \quad \forall i \end{aligned}$$

Note that these problems are equivalent in the sense that, at the optimum, they reach the same points and equal the same value. Relaxing the constraints over b_i , we can further reformulate the problem as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}} \quad & \sum_i \frac{a_i^2}{b_i} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \\ & \sqrt{A_i(\mathbf{x})} \leq a_i \quad \forall i \\ & -B_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq -b_i \quad \forall i \end{aligned}$$

We will later show that $b_i \geq 0$ holds at the optimum.

The partial Lagrangian considering only the \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} variables, is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) &= \sum_i \frac{a_i^2}{b_i} + \mathbf{z}_1^T (\sqrt{\mathbf{A}(x)} - \mathbf{a}) + \mathbf{z}_2^T (-\mathbf{B}(x) + \mathbf{b}) \\ &= \sum_i \left(\frac{a_i^2}{b_i} + z_{i,1} (\sqrt{A_i(x)} - a_i) + z_{i,2} (-B_i(x) + b_i) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Then the partial Lagrangian is jointly convex over \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} with fixed \mathbf{x} . At the optimal, it must hold that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial a_i} = 2 \frac{a_i}{b_i} - z_{i,1} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial b_i} = -\frac{a_i^2}{b_i^2} + z_{i,2} = 0$$

This implies that $z_{i,1}^2 = 4z_{i,2}$. Then, replace this in the Lagrangian as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{z}) = \sum_i \left(\frac{a_i^2}{b_i} + z_i \left(\sqrt{A_i(x)} - a_i \right) + \frac{1}{4} z_i^2 (-B_i(x) + b_i) \right)$$

Furthermore, from the previous conditions we have that $b_i = 2\frac{a_i}{z_i}$. If $A_i(x) \geq 0$ and $z_i > 0$, then $b_i \geq 0$. Then, after some work, the Lagrangian can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \sum_i \left(z_i \sqrt{A_i(x)} - \left(\frac{z_i}{2} \right)^2 B_i(x) \right)$$

We can, without loss of generality, make a change of variable $\hat{z}_i = \frac{z_i}{2}$. Then, we have

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = \sum_i \left(2\hat{z}_i \sqrt{A_i(x)} - \hat{z}_i^2 B_i(x) \right)$$

This form is the same as applying the QT on (48) directly. Then, the QT in minimization problems is equivalent to a primal-dual technique, in which the augmented Lagrangian is minimized in the primal optimization step, and maximized on the dual variable update step.

APPENDIX D

OPTIMAL POWER FOR PARTIAL UAV ALLOCATION

Let us write the partial Lagrangian of optimization problem (62) considering only the maximum power constraint as

$$\mathcal{L}(p_{u,h}, p_{u,s}, \lambda) = \sum_{k \in \{h,s\}} \left(\frac{a_k}{R_{u,k}} + \lambda p_{u,k} \right) - \lambda P_u$$

This is clearly a convex function on both primal variables. Thus, we derivate this with respect to the primal variables and equal the expression to 0 to obtain the global optimum, and we obtain

$$\lambda = \frac{\zeta_k a_k \log(2)}{B_k (1 + \zeta_k p_{u,k}) (\log(1 + \zeta_k p_{u,k}))^2} \quad (71)$$

for $k \in \{h, s\}$. Then, equaling the expressions for both we obtain

$$\frac{\zeta_h a_h \log(2)}{B_h (1 + \zeta_h p_{u,h}) (\log(1 + \zeta_h p_{u,h}))^2} = \frac{\zeta_s a_s \log(2)}{B_s (1 + \zeta_s p_{u,s}) (\log(1 + \zeta_s p_{u,s}))^2} \quad (72)$$

It can be clearly seen that the original objective function (62a) is minimized by using all of the available power between both links. Thus, we can write $p_{u,s} = P_u - p_{u,h}$, and rearranging (72), we obtain (64).

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